

Assessing the Impact of Nutrient Limitation on Tropical Vegetation Carbon Dynamics under Historical and Future Climate Scenarios using a flexible-trait LPJmL-FIT Dynamic Global Vegetation Model

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Abstract

Tropical forests worldwide play a crucial role in sequestering carbon emissions globally from the atmosphere into the trees and soil. The effect of carbon dioxide fertilization on tropical forests has been higher than in other ecosystems in terms of carbon uptake. The strength of this effect has been reduced over time due to extreme temperatures, droughts, and nutrient limitations. The size and variability of the land-based CO₂ sink remain uncertain, in part because global data on ecosystem nitrogen (N) cycling are limited. Along with long-term field experiments to better understand the dynamics of terrestrial carbon (C) uptake and other parameters of biogeochemical cycles, researchers utilize complex Dynamic Global Vegetation Models (DGVMs). But if ecosystem models do not account for N limitations, they may overestimate the gains from CO₂ fertilization and CO₂-driven increases in water-use efficiency. To understand this gap, this study employs an advanced dynamic vegetation model called Lund-Potsdam-Jena managed Land - Flexible Individual Traits (LPJmL-FIT), which incorporates nitrogen limitations to assess N and C dynamics under historical and climate change scenarios (SSP126 and SSP370) in the tropical biomes of Brazil. The results, including nitrogen constraints, substantially reduce terrestrial carbon uptake, with historical (1985-2014 years) gross primary productivity (GPP) and net primary productivity (NPP) declining by 10-12% and future (2015-2100 years) vegetation carbon (VegC) and NPP falling by 16-19% and 12-14% under SSP126 and SSP370 respectively, in comparison to simulations without nitrogen constraints, highlighting strong and increasing nitrogen limitation on tropical productivity. Using the model's ability to simulate continuous shifts in key plant functional traits under rising CO₂, the analyses at Santarém and Manaus study sites in Brazil, show that nitrogen treatments fundamentally altered trait-productivity relationships: under unlimited N, structural traits dominated GPP, whereas nitrogen limitation increased the influence of foliar traits such as leaf carbon to nitrogen ratio and specific leaf area (SLA) over the recent decades. By analyzing different methods and reviewing existing literature, this study finds that the CO₂ fertilization effect in tropical forests is weakening, with future projections showing further declines.

Keywords: DGVMs; nitrogen limitations; tropical forests; LPJmL-FIT; CO₂ fertilization effect; plant functional traits; GPP; NPP; vegetation carbon

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List of Abbreviations

DGVMs	Dynamic Global Vegetation Models
LPJ	Lund-Potsdam-Jena Model
LPJmL-FIT	Lund-Potsdam-Jena managed Land - Flexible Individual Traits
f_legume	Initial proportion of nitrogen-fixing plants
ISIMIP	Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathway
PFTs	Plant Functional Types
NLIM	Nitrogen-limited (limited nitrogen availability)
UNLIM	Unlimited nitrogen (unlimited nitrogen availability)
GPP	Gross Primary Productivity
VegC	Vegetation Carbon
NPP	Net Primary Productivity
MK Test	Mann-Kendall Statistical Test
CFE	Carbon-dioxide Fertilisation Effect
BNF	Biological Nitrogen Fixation
SLA	Specific Leaf Area
LNC	Leaf Nitrogen Content
Leaf C	Individual Tree Leaf Carbon
Leaf N	Individual Tree Leaf Nitrogen
LES	Leaf Economic Spectrum
N	Nitrogen
P	Phosphorus
C	Carbon

1. Introduction

Climate change, driven by increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, poses a significant threat to global ecosystems, particularly forests, which play a crucial role in carbon sequestration and the regulation of Earth's climate (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2021, 2023). Understanding the forest's response to elevated CO₂ and related climate changes is critical for predicting future climate trajectories and developing effective mitigation and adaptation strategies. When levels of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere rise, terrestrial ecosystems absorb more carbon due to increased photosynthesis, resulting in higher water use efficiency of trees, a phenomenon known as CO₂ fertilization. One possible outcome of elevated carbon uptake is the buildup of extra carbon in plant biomass, especially in woody tissue, which can boost ecosystem carbon storage because of the relatively long turnover times (Norby et al., 2024). Forests have remained a major global carbon sink, consistently absorbing around 2.4-3.6 Pg C yr⁻¹ since the 1990s, enhancing growth and carbon uptake, particularly in temperate and regrown tropical forests (Pan et al., 2024). However, tropical forests (especially in the Amazon) and boreal forests show declining carbon sequestration due to disturbances, area loss, nutrient limitations, and signs of sink saturation (Hubau et al., 2020; Pan et al., 2011; Pan et al., 2024; Sitch et al., 2015).

For a long time, it has been proposed that CO₂ fertilization could help reduce the pace at which atmospheric CO₂ concentration grows, which may help lessen the effects of climate change (Keeling et al., 1996). However, the issue of nutrient availability affects carbon fixation by vegetation, impacting the estimation of the remaining carbon budget (Ågren et al., 2012; Sisto & MacDougall, 2024). A major debated question in global biogeochemistry is how soil nitrogen availability influences terrestrial carbon storage, a source of major uncertainty in forecasting future land-based carbon sequestration (Luo et al., 2004).

Plant growth in terrestrial ecosystems is frequently constrained by the availability of nitrogen (N) or phosphorus (P) (Güsewell, 2004). The multiple limitation hypothesis proposes that plants regulate their growth so that several resources can simultaneously limit growth (Bloom et al., 1985). Potential effects of nutrient limitation, specifically N and P, must be considered in the estimation of the terrestrial carbon sink. Ignoring these limitations could lead to an overestimation of the land's capacity

to absorb carbon and could lead to unrealistically high projections of the carbon sink (Wieder et al., 2015).

The scientific community has made important progress in understanding the effects of increased CO₂ and nitrogen availability on plants and ecosystems. Experiments in different ecosystems have shown that higher CO₂ can boost plant growth and carbon storage (Ainsworth & Long, 2005; Norby et al., 2010). The interactions between carbon and nitrogen are fundamental in shaping terrestrial ecosystem responses to elevated atmospheric CO₂, from the leaf level to global scales, and across both short- and long-term timescales. While CO₂ fertilization effects can stimulate plant growth, the availability of other resources, like nitrogen, can significantly constrain this response (Reich et al., 2006a; Reich et al., 2006b). N availability is responsible for 65% global vegetation's elevated CO₂ fertilization response (Terrer et al., 2019).

Nitrogen limitation can interact with increased CO₂ in complex ways. This interaction affects plant physiology, the distribution of traits, and processes at the ecosystem level (Hungate et al., 2003). The global nitrogen and carbon cycles are closely interconnected, and the effects of N on ecosystems can vary depending on geographic location within specific biomes (LeBauer & Treseder, 2008).

The study conducted by Vitousek & Matson (1988) in 33 sites across 5 tropical areas concluded that in relative to temperate forests N availability in lowland tropical forests was adequate unlike the lowland white sand sites and upper montane sites, where N could be in short supply and potentially limiting to biological activity in these naturally infertile or cool sites. In Brazil, wet biomes like Amazon rainforests, P limitation is found to be constraining the productivity by various studies (Fleischer et al., 2019; Vitousek, 1984). Similarly, in the dry biomes, like in the tropical savannas of the Cerrado biome's productivity is further constrained by water availability disruption of nutrient coupling between N and P (Bustamante et al., 2012b; Da Lacerda et al., 2024). Rather, P limitation dominates, while N is a secondary limitation that becomes relevant at regular intervals due to seasonal conditions (Du et al., 2020; Norby et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2014) and can occur in the event of a disturbance with associated N losses during succession (Winbourne et al., 2018).

Now, the necessity to understand these biogeochemical limitations, along with the increasing interactions of CO₂ concentration, becomes more important for terrestrial plants. To compensate for these drivers of global changes in the resources, especially nutrient constraints, terrestrial plants are forced to adopt specific physiological and

morphological strategies captured by functional traits (García et al., 2022; Reich, 2014; Sardans & Peñuelas, 2012).

Furthermore, how plants adapt to changing environments is crucial for long-term ecosystem responses. Changes in plant traits, like specific leaf area (SLA) and leaf N content (LNC), can affect plant growth, resource use efficiency, and competitive interactions (Díaz et al., 2007). This N limitation is evident in young secondary tropical forests (Davidson et al., 2004). A drop in LNC lowers photosynthetic capacity, which limits the positive response of vegetation to higher CO₂ levels (He et al., 2017). Research has also looked into how plant traits affect ecosystem responses to environmental changes. The Leaf Economic Spectrum (LES) concept offers a way to understand how plants adjust to varying resource availability, describing the coordinated changes in key chemical, structural, and physiological properties of leaves, such as SLA and leaf dry mass per unit area (LMA) (Wright et al., 2004). The reliable quantification of this spectrum and its interaction with climate is deemed valuable for modelling nutrient fluxes and vegetation boundaries under changing land-use and climate (Onoda et al., 2017).

Additionally, changes in plant traits like SLA and root allocation can affect how species interact and how communities function (Poorter & Pérez-Soba, 2002). Considering climatic factors, traits like SLA and leaf thickness relate to the slope of abundance-temperature relationships. This indicates that species with certain functional traits might react more to temperature changes, affecting their abundance over time (Soudzilovskaia et al., 2013).

Plants change their traits along the LES based on CO₂ availability. At low CO₂, plants have higher SLA, higher leaf N, and lower respiration rates. This indicates a shift toward “fast” traits that maximize carbon gain per unit mass. At higher CO₂, traits move toward the “slow” end, showing lower SLA, lower N, and higher respiration. This allows plants to grow faster while developing sturdier, resource-conserving leaves. These responses differ among species, but they show a general shift in carbon costs and assimilation rates according to ambient CO₂ levels (Temme et al., 2017).

Dynamic Global Vegetation Models (DGVMs) are advanced tools used to understand vegetation-atmosphere interactions and simulate vegetation distribution and related biogeochemical processes across past, present, and future scenarios. Over the past decade, DGVMs have seen significant advancements in how they represent physical,

hydrological, and biogeochemical processes like photosynthesis, respiration, fire, permafrost, and regional vegetation characteristics. Models like LPJmL (Lund–Potsdam–Jena managed Land) are created to improve land-use dynamics, such as the role of agriculture in the global climate-vegetation systems (Bondeau et al., 2007; Schaphoff et al., 2018).

Nevertheless, important limitations remain, in the current model's capacity to explicitly capture the mechanisms of functional biodiversity, such as trait-mediated competition and species co-existence, which are vital for realistic simulations of ecosystem dynamics and stability in natural vegetation (Quillet et al., 2010; Scheiter et al., 2013). To improve climate predictions, there is a need of better treatment of plant allocation, N limits, and microbial feedback (Stocker et al., 2025; Zou et al., 2023). If ecosystem models overlook N limitations, they might overstate the impact of CO₂ fertilization and the related gains in water use efficiency (He et al., 2017). The size and variability of the terrestrial CO₂ sink are still unclear because of limited global data on ecosystem N cycles. A global nutrient limitation map generated using remote sensing showed that nutrient constraints reduce overall plant productivity by approximately 16–28% worldwide compared to the hypothetical maximum potential productivity dictated by first-order climatic and energy controls (Fisher et al., 2012).

The free-air CO₂ enrichment (FACE) experiment in a deciduous sweetgum forest showed that increased CO₂ initially raised net primary productivity (NPP) by 24%, but this increase fell to 9% over 11 years, which was linked to decreasing N availability as the forest matured, impacting the long-term growth response to elevated CO₂ (Norby et al., 2010).

Initial studies performed by Thornton et al. (2007), on the Community Land Model (CLM 3.0), introducing the terrestrial C-N coupling reduces the simulated global terrestrial carbon uptake response to increasing CO₂ concentration to around 74% in comparison to the model version considering only carbon.

In contrast, N limitation is more significant in temperate, boreal, and high-altitude regions, whereas tropical areas limited by P contribute more to overall productivity and biomass. With more information and data on P limitation becoming available, some DGVMs could model the related processes in their biogeochemistry and study co-limitation effects (Goll et al., 2017). Having forest gap dynamics embedded, advanced DGVMs, such as LPJ-GUESS, which incorporate P limitation into their features,

improve predictions of global vegetation and soil carbon, N, and P stocks. The CNP (Carbon-Nitrogen-Phosphorus) model simulation more closely matches observed global biomass. Over the 20th-21st centuries, N limitation decreased, and P limitation increased, highlighting the importance of P dynamics for accurate carbon cycle simulations (Dantas de Paula et al., 2025).

In their study of a new model version of LPJ-GUESS-NTD (the Lund-Potsdam-Jena General Ecosystem Simulator-Nutrient-Trait Dynamics), by Dantas de Paula et al. (2021), they have examined the trait-nutrient processes in tropical forests.

However, the precise nature of plant trait adjustments under combined elevated CO₂ and N limitation effect, and their consequences for ecosystem functioning remain poorly understood (van Bodegom et al., 2014). Despite the new advancements, significant knowledge gaps remain which hinder our ability to accurately project forest responses to future climate change. Firstly, there is a need for improved models that capture the interactions between CO₂, N, and flexible plant traits. Current models often oversimplify these processes, which creates uncertainties in future projections. Second, further research is needed to understand how plant traits change their strategies, when CO₂ levels rise while N remains limited. The third need is to look more closely at how these interactions vary in space and time. How do they differ across different biomes of Brazilian ecosystems and over extended periods?

Filling in these knowledge gaps is vital for predicting how plants and ecosystems will respond to climate change. A better understanding of how traits trade off under increased CO₂ and limited N will allow for a more accurate representation of plant behaviour and adaptation in ecosystem models. This understanding will also lead to more trustworthy projections of future ecosystem function.

This thesis addresses these knowledge gaps by utilizing another advanced dynamic global vegetation model that simulates individual trees with flexible individual traits, LPJmL-FIT (Lund-Potsdam-Jena managed Land-Flexible Individual Traits) (Sakschewski et al., 2015), and incorporates interactions between carbon, N, and plant traits. By performing a series of model experiments, this thesis will investigate how N limitation influences the CO₂ fertilization effect, and how plant trait distributions respond to these combined pressures. This work will contribute to a better understanding of forest dynamics under current and future climate conditions, utilizing CMIP6 climate scenarios, and inform strategies for sustainable forest management.

Thereby, this thesis aims to answer the following questions:

1. How does N limitation in the LPJmL-FIT model simulations influence the CO₂ fertilization effect and regulate vegetation productivity dynamics under climate change in tropical forests of Brazil?
2. How do relationships between plant functional traits reflect adjustments under elevated CO₂ and N limitation?
3. How do N availability and tree traits affect ecosystem functioning at the tree level, and what do model predictions indicate about forest adaptation and ecosystem responses to future climate change?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

For the simulation experiments, Brazil was selected as the study area in the tropics. In global simulations of this model version with N limitation, two plant functional types (PFTs), temperate broad-leaved evergreen and temperate broad-leaved summer green, were not well represented in the results. Focusing on Brazil allowed us to address this issue while also increasing the number of simulation patches by restricting the study domain to a single tropical country rather than the entire tropical forest region.

Brazil spans a vast geographic range, extending approximately from 5° N to 34° S in latitude and from 35° W to 74° W in longitude. Furthermore, to understand the importance of analyzing tree functional traits, two sites in the Amazon rainforest: Santarém (-2.75 (latitude), -54.75 (longitude)) and Manaus (-3.25 (latitude), -60.25 (longitude)) were selected (see Figure 1). Brazil's biomes comprise the world's most ecologically diverse and threatened ecosystems, including the Amazon, Cerrado, Atlantic Forest (Mata Atlântica), Caatinga, Pampa, and Pantanal.

Moreover, land-use and cover change (e.g., deforestation, pasture, and soy agriculture) are reshaping Brazil's biomes in complex ways. Studies using high-resolution data show that the loss of primary and secondary natural vegetation continues in Brazil, particularly in the Cerrado and Amazon biomes, where agricultural intensification is highly pronounced in biome transition zones (Caballero et al., 2023).

However, this influence was not considered in this study due to the complexity of the topic and the time constraints of the thesis.

Figure 1: Map depicting the biomes and the two locations (Santarém and Manaus) as the study area in Brazil

2.2 LPJmL-FIT Model

The Lund–Potsdam–Jena Dynamic Global Vegetation Model (LPJ) integrates process-based, large-scale simulations of terrestrial vegetation dynamics with land–atmosphere carbon and water interactions within a modular system (Sitch et al., 2003). The Lund–Potsdam–Jena managed land (LPJmL) model has been consistently advanced since its first publication to more accurately simulate the effects of human activities and climate change by incorporating detailed features, such as improved hydrological, biogeochemical, and vegetation dynamics, including crop types and permafrost schemes (Schaphoff et al., 2018).

The LPJmL-FIT model is an advanced, flexible trait DGVM that extends the LPJmL framework by incorporating plant functional traits to improve predictions of ecosystem responses to environmental changes. It explicitly simulates key leaf traits such as specific leaf area (SLA), leaf N content, and maximum carboxylation rate (V_{cmax}),

which are critical for understanding plant productivity and carbon-water dynamics (Sakschewski et al., 2015). The model incorporates the three theories of LES, Stem Economics Spectrum (SES), and Forest Gap Dynamics. The model has been applied to simulate natural forest ecosystems across climatic gradients, capturing variations in functional diversity and species adaptation strategies (Thonicke et al., 2020).

By integrating functional diversity, LPJmL-FIT can assess vegetation dynamics, competition, and trade-offs in response to climate variability and N availability, representing functional diversity within several PFTs (Billing et al., 2024). The model operates using daily climate input data, including temperature, precipitation, radiation, as well as atmospheric CO₂ concentration and soil texture, which influence soil hydrology. Vegetation dynamics are modeled within independent 10 m × 10 m forest patches, where each tree's growth and survival depend on photosynthesis, respiration, and competition for light and water. Over time, these factors alone determine which trees thrive and which ones die. In the LPJmL-FIT model, traits are constrained within globally observed ranges, creating a multidimensional space of all ecologically possible trait combinations. Each tree begins with a unique, randomly assigned trait set, all equally probable. Through competition initially without N limitation for light and water, the combinations best suited to local environmental conditions dominate. By simulating individual trees based on their traits, the model effectively predicts natural trait distributions and realistically represents functional diversity. Greater functional diversity, in turn, enhances ecosystem functioning, stability, productivity, and resilience to disturbances and environmental change (Sakschewski et al., 2015). Each tree individual is classified into one of four primary PFTs: temperate broad-leaved summergreen, temperate broad-leaved evergreen, boreal needle-leaved evergreen, and temperate needle-leaved evergreen (Billing et al., 2024). The original LPJmL model overlooked the established positive relationship between leaf N content (N_{area}) and photosynthetic capacity ($V_{cmaxarea}$), calculating $V_{cmaxarea}$ solely based on external factors. LPJmL-FIT was developed to rectify this by mechanistically linking $V_{cmaxarea}$ to N_{area} (which is derived from SLA, thereby integrating crucial physiological trade-offs into the model (Sakschewski et al., 2015).

The model currently represents forests without accounting for human activities such as management, meaning its outputs reflect purely natural forest dynamics (Billing et al., 2024). Previous studies have validated the model's accuracy in simulating trait

composition, biomass, tree height, and mortality for tropical rainforests and European natural forests (Sakschewski et al., 2015; Thonicke et al., 2020).

This video by Billing et al. (2024) (available at: https://www.pik-potsdam.de/~billing/video/2023/spinup_LPJmLFIT.mp4) visualizes forest community assembly where individual trees, established with random SLA and Wood Density (WD) traits, undergo rigorous environmental and competitive filtering. The final forest structure results from the survival and growth of the fittest trait combinations in response to the local climate and existing vegetation.

2.2.1 Plant Traits in LPJmL-FIT

LPJmL-FIT relies on plant functional traits to constrain vegetation dynamics, productivity, biomass allocation, and water use. Therefore, trait selection is directly linked to the model's parameterization and overall behaviour. This subsection provides a concise overview of the key traits used in LPJmL-FIT and explains their ecological relevance in the context of model processes.

The three important elements, Carbon (C), Nitrogen (N), and Phosphorus (P), plays an important role in plant functioning, affecting their overall growth and adaptations (Cao & Chen, 2017). The levels of C, N, and P in plant leaves are key indicators of nutrient use strategies and are critical factors influencing plant growth, reproduction, and overall ecosystem function in response to environmental shifts (Qin et al., 2019). Depending on the forest types and growth stages, the leaf stoichiometry changes (M. Wang et al., 2017). The ratio of leaf C:N, and C:P are very important physiological indices for plant growth rate and carbon sequestration ability (Ågren, 2004). Under severe N limitation, plants increase their C:N ratio to prioritize survival by boosting nitrogen use efficiency, while in less N-limited environments, a lower C:N ratio supports growth prioritization. Within N-limited forests, different plant organs maintain a convergent overall direction of C:N change, but their varying rates of change ensure the plant achieves optimal survival (Zhang et al., 2020).

Specific leaf area (SLA) refers to the ratio of a leaf's surface area to its dry mass, which acts as an indicator of leaf thickness, with higher SLA values generally representing thinner leaves (Hatfield & Dold, 2019). Plants grown under high light intensity develop leaves with low SLA, meaning their leaves are thicker compared to those grown under

low light conditions (Evans & Poorter, 2001). This suggests that leaf structure adjusts to the surrounding light environment to enhance light capture.

N content per unit leaf area (N_{area}) is an important trait in plant functional ecology and biogeochemical studies. It consists of two main components: a structural fraction that correlates with leaf mass per area (LMA), and a metabolic fraction that is associated with Rubisco activity and photosynthetic capacity (Dong et al., 2017).

2.3 Nitrogen Limitation in LPJmL-FIT Model

Nitrogen is an essential mineral element for plant growth; however, low N stress severely reduces yield. After absorption, N regulates key biological processes, including phytohormones, microRNA (miRNA), root development, and mycorrhizal symbiosis, to help plants cope with environmental challenges (Q. Wang et al., 2024).

Biological Nitrogen Fixation (BNF) is the conversion of atmospheric N to readily assimilable ammonia (NH_3) catalyzed by the Nase enzyme within specialized prokaryotes. This crucial process is performed by diverse organisms, including cyanobacteria, free-living soil bacteria like *Azotobacter*, and, most importantly, symbiotic bacteria (e.g., *Rhizobium*) associated with legumes (Postgate, 1982).

Since BNF plays an important role in fixing the global N cycle, it becomes important to correctly quantify the fixation amount for understanding the C and N dynamics using vegetation models that link plant physiology with vegetation dynamics and biogeochemical cycles.

The groundwork for implementing N limitation in the LPJmL was already done by Bloh et al. (2018) using simple empirical relationships for calculating BNF for natural vegetation as a function of long-term average annual evapotranspiration, and setting crop legume BNF equal to the entire plant N deficit, inspired by Cleveland et al. (1999). This was further improved by Wirth et al. (2024) by incorporating the "C-Costly" BNF approach, which incorporates explicit constraints based on soil temperature and soil water content using PFT-specific functions, and limits BNF based on the plant's N deficit and whether the associated C cost (respiratory loss of C) exceeds the fraction of Net Primary Production (f_{NPP}) available for fixation.

In the LPJmL-FIT model, plant N requirements are initially met by utilizing N stored within plant tissues, with any additional demand being satisfied from soil nitrate and

ammonium pools, which do not require additional carbon investment. If these sources are insufficient, plants capable of BNF supplement their N supply (Bergmann, 2024). The BNF process is adapted from the standard LPJmL model for individual-based simulation, and fixation rates are expressed as area-based monthly fluxes influenced by soil temperature and moisture conditions (Wirth et al., 2024). Fixation occurs facultatively, meaning that trees activate BNF only when N demand exceeds supply, and deactivate it when N is sufficient (Menge et al., 2014; Wong et al., 2020). The model estimates the carbon cost of N fixation by multiplying the carbon required per unit N fixed by the fixation rate and then compares this cost with the portion of NPP available for fixation. If the carbon cost exceeds this available NPP, the plant fixes only as much N as its energy budget allows (Wirth et al., 2024).

From the previous work of Bergmann (2024) a key innovation in LPJmL-FIT is the explicit modeling of individual N-fixing trees through the parameter f_legume , which defines the probability that a newly initialized tree can fix N, allowing the proportion of fixers to change dynamically over time. Only trees initialized as fixers perform BNF, and the potential fixation rate for each fixer is adjusted relative to the proportion of fixers in the population. It appears in the equations only to convert the area-based fixation rate of the standard model into a per-fixer rate by dividing by the fraction of fixers. Once each tree is assigned as a fixer or non-fixer, f_legume is no longer needed, since fixation then depends solely on the individual tree's carbon availability, nitrogen deficit, and environmental conditions.

Calculation of Potential Fixation:

The total daily fixation for a given area is calculated as:

$$\text{total amount} = N_{\text{fix,pot}}(\text{total}) \times \text{total area} \quad \dots(1)$$

where $N_{\text{fix,pot}}(\text{total})$ is the potential fixation rate in the standard model [$\text{g m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$] and total area is the size of the area considered [m^2].

The potential fixation rate must be adjusted for modelling in LPJmLFIT so that it represents the rate of fixing plants. To obtain the area-based potential fixation rate for the fixing trees, the total fixation is divided by the area fraction occupied by fixers:

$$N_{\text{fix,pot}}(\text{fixer}) = \frac{\text{total amount}}{f_{\text{legume}} \times \text{total area}} = \frac{N_{\text{fix,pot}}(\text{total})}{f_{\text{legume}}} \quad \dots(2)$$

This approach allows the proportion of N-fixing plants to vary dynamically in response to environmental N availability (Bergmann, 2024). As the total area is included in both the fixing plants, the quotient of the potential fixation rate in the standard model and this total quantity, and in the denominator, it is cancelled out, and the fixation rate of the proportion of fixing plants (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Schematic Representation of the modeling of N limitation in the LPJmL-FIT model. Green: newly added elements compared to the standard LPJmL model; red: removed elements. This figure is copied from a previous master's thesis work by Bergmann (2024). Created using the free online software: drawio.com

The maximum amount of NPP available for fixation is shown per tree in the LPJmL-FIT model, so that a reduction by the proportion of fixing plants is not necessary here, and the multiplication by the factor f_{legume} can be removed (see Figure 2).

Under low N conditions, fixers gain a competitive advantage and may become more dominant, whereas under high N availability, fixation becomes costly and fewer fixers are favored (Allen et al., 2011; Taylor et al., 2019). By integrating these mechanisms, LPJmL-FIT realistically simulates N limitation, individual plant strategies, and competition between fixing and non-fixing species, enabling more accurate predictions of ecosystem productivity and functional dynamics.

In this thesis, one of the goals of model development also includes testing the new development of N limitation in the LPJmL-FIT model by analyzing the output produced from the simulations. It provided an opportunity to understand the process dynamics and shortcomings of the N limitation feature on different biomes through the process of analysis and validation of the model outputs.

2.4 Study Design

This section provides an overview of how the experiments were structured to evaluate the combined and individual effects of nitrogen availability and atmospheric CO₂ concentration in the LPJmL-FIT model.

2.4.1 Model Configuration and Experimental Setup

The simulation experiments are performed on LPJmL-FIT version 5.6.004 on the new High-Performance Computing (HPC) system at the Potsdam Institute of Climate Impact Research facility.

The LPJmL-FIT simulations were initiated for each grid cell in the simulation domain, i.e., Brazil, from bare-ground conditions, allowing vegetation and soil C-N pools to reach equilibrium through a spin-up phase of 3000 years, repeatedly cycling through 30 years of climate input data, thereby stabilizing ecosystem dynamics before the transient simulation. After equilibrium was reached, the simulation continued through the transient period, spanning from 1850 to 2014 (historical scenario).

For future projections and simulations, two SSP scenarios: the sustainable scenario (SSP126) and the regional rivalry scenario (SSP370) were considered, covering the years from 2015 to 2100. This thesis focuses exclusively on natural vegetation; therefore, land-use changes implied in the SSP storylines are not considered. Complete details of these scenarios are presented in Table 1.

1. General Experiment Setup:

To understand the effects of N limitation, the factorial simulations were done with two conditions: a) When N availability was not limited (UNLIM case), b) When N availability was limited (NLIM case)

Six sets of outputs were generated for all three scenarios (Historical, SSP126, and SSP370) for both UNLIM and NLIM cases, covering all three scenarios. In tropical regions specifically, data on the rates of N-fixing plants is scarce, and the available

information is inconsistent, with estimates varying between 5% and 25% (Cleveland et al., 1999).

Table 1: Overview of SSP-RCP scenarios used for simulating the climate scenarios for this study, showing an increase in radiative forcing and a projected increase in temperature. Very likely range =90 percent confidence interval of the estimate (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2021, 2023).

SSP-RCP	Description	Radiative Forcing (2100) [W/m ²]	Mid-Term (2041-2060)		Long-Term (2081-2100)	
			Best Estimate (°C)	Very likely range (°C)	Best Estimate (°C)	Very likely range (°C)
SSP126	Low emissions – sustainability and strong climate policy, resulting in low climate change	2.6	1.6	1.0-2.3	1.8	1.3-2.4
SSP370	High emissions – regional rivalry, slow development, resulting in intensive climate change	7.0	2.1	1.5-3.0	3.6	2.8-4.6

Bergmann (2024), varied the parameter f_{legume} for different simulations (0%, 1.5%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25%) and validated the results against observational data to determine which percentage provided the most realistic results. In this study, the results that yielded the most realistic outcomes were taken while setting N availability to the limiting mode. The regional legume fractions or f_{legume} were kept at 15% for tropical, 5% for temperate, and 9% for boreal zones, which were kept at 5% for tropical, 1% for temperate, and 3% for boreal zones by Wirth et al. (2024).

The model used spatial patches to capture site-level heterogeneity, with a fixed random seed (7) ensuring reproducibility. The independent forest patches in the model are of size 10 m × 10 m (Sakschewski et al., 2015). For the UNLIM case, 300 patches

were simulated, and for the NLIM case, 250 patches were simulated, corresponding to approximately 3.5 ha and 2.5 ha of forest area in each grid cell, respectively.

2. Sensitivity Analysis Setup:

The following set of settings was changed in the general experiment setup to enhance the understanding of N availability and its limitations:

- a. To assess the impact of varying the BNF ratio on the model output for both NLIM and UNLIM cases, additional experiments were carried out, in which the ratio was first doubled and then halved from the baseline settings described above. These experiments provided further insight into how changes in N availability influence the GPP values.
- b. For another sensitivity analysis, atmospheric CO₂ concentrations were kept constant at their 1901 levels (approximately 296 ppm). This constant-CO₂ sensitivity run allows us to isolate the effects driven by CO₂ concentration changes from those caused by climate variability.

2.4.2 Climate Data Inputs

For this study, climate input data were obtained from the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP3b) bias-adjusted atmospheric dataset (Lange & Büchner, 2021). The ISIMIP initiative provides a standardized framework designed to enhance the consistency and comparability of climate impact simulations across different models and sectors. The ISIMIP3b dataset delivers daily climate variables at a 0.5° spatial resolution, including temperature, precipitation, shortwave radiation, and longwave radiation, all of which were used as climate forcing inputs in this study's simulations. The dataset was bias-corrected and statistically downscaled using the ISIMIP3BASD method, which applies trend-preserving parametric quantile mapping to minimize systematic errors while maintaining long-term climate trends and realistic variability (Lange, 2019). This approach ensures that the adjusted data remain physically consistent across variables and models. Additionally, CO₂ concentration changes were incorporated according to the ISIMIP protocol to maintain coherence with the associated socioeconomic and emission scenarios. In this study, the Max Planck Institute Earth System Model (MPI-ESM1.2-LR) was used as the primary climate forcing source within the ISIMIP3b framework. The MPI model, developed by the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (Germany), is widely recognized for its robust

representation of large-scale atmospheric circulation and land–atmosphere feedback. Previous studies have successfully applied MPI-based climate forcing in ecosystem and hydrological modeling due to its consistent performance across global and regional scales (Giorgetta et al., 2013; Lange & Büchner, 2021). The choice of MPI ensures stable and realistic climate trajectories, as well as comparability with other ISIMIP3b impact simulations.

2.5 Data Processing and Analysis

The post-data analysis was performed using the free programming language R version 4.4.0. (R Core Team, 2024).

To analyze differences in outputs among PFTs between NLIM and UNLIM simulations, the `lpjmlstats` package was utilised (Hötten et al., 2025). This package provides statistical tools tailored for LPJmL model outputs, enabling comparison and summarization of simulation results across PFTs.

The main outputs of the model analyzed are gross primary productivity (GPP) in $\text{gC}/\text{m}^2/\text{month}$ and vegetation carbon (VegC), which comprises both above- and below-ground annual biomass in gC/m^2 .

Furthermore, the following statistical tests and analyses were conducted on the model results. These analyses will help reveal the impact of changes in N limitation on forest productivity and trends under different climate scenarios, which is the first research question of this study. For the second study question of this thesis, regression analysis will be employed to investigate the relationship between plant functional traits derived from the model output. Furthermore, for the third study question, advanced machine learning techniques will enhance the understanding of plant functional traits under N limitations.

2.5.1 Mann-Kendall and Sen’s Slope Tests

The trends in the time series plots of the outputs, such as GPP and VegC, are being assessed using the Mann-Kendall (MK) and Sen’s slope tests. These tests were conducted for both the treatment experiments (UNLIM/NLIM) outputs. Both tests are widely used non-parametric statistical methods for detecting and quantifying monotonic trends in time series data that do not assume normal data distribution and

are robust against missing values and outliers (Kendall, 1975; Mann, 1945; Sen, 1968).

The MK test evaluates whether a monotonic trend exists. For a time series (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) , the test statistic S is calculated as:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_i), \quad \dots(3)$$

$$\text{sgn}(x_j - x_i) = \begin{cases} +1, & x_j - x_i > 0 \\ 0, & x_j - x_i = 0 \\ -1, & x_j - x_i < 0 \end{cases} \quad \dots(4)$$

For large n , S is approximately normally distributed with a mean $E(S) = 0$ and variance:

$$\text{Var}(S) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{i=1}^m t_i(t_i-1)(2t_i+5)}{18} \quad \dots(5)$$

where m is the number of tied groups and t_i is the size of each tied group. The standardized test statistic Z is:

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}}, & S > 0 \\ 0, & S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(S)}}, & S < 0 \end{cases} \quad \dots(6)$$

The p-value is derived from the standard normal distribution of Z . The trend is considered statistically significant at the 95% confidence level if $p < 0.05$; otherwise ($p \geq 0.05$), it is not significant.

Kendall's tau (τ) quantifies trend strength:

$$\tau = \frac{S}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}n(n-1)}} \quad \dots(7)$$

To estimate the trend magnitude, Sen's slope estimator was used. The slopes of all pairs (x_i, x_j) are:

$$Q_{ij} = \frac{x_j - x_i}{j - i}; i < j \quad \dots(8)$$

The median of these slopes gives Sen's slope Q :

$$Q = \text{median}(Q_{ij}) \quad \dots(9)$$

A positive Q indicates an increasing trend, while a negative Q indicates a decreasing trend. Together, the MK test and Sen's slope provide a robust analysis of trend significance and magnitude in the dataset.

2.5.2 Beta Factor Calculation

Analysing the beta (β) factor as a metric to quantify the strength of CO₂ fertilization under varying nutrient conditions helps to understand plant responses to elevated CO₂. The factor was first introduced by Keeling (1973) as 'degree of CO₂ fertilization,' to express a logarithmic dependence of plant productivity response to rising atmospheric CO₂ concentrations.

In this study, this metric is used to highlight how nutrient availability impacts the CO₂ fertilization effect (CFE). Preliminary findings show divergent trends in the fertilization effect when applying these methods, showing that the β factor's utility may vary depending on the study assumptions and data sources (Fleischer & Terrer, 2022; Huang et al., 2015).

In this study to assess the CFE across historical and future scenarios, two distinct methodologies were implemented for calculating the β factor, drawing from the approaches outlined in S. Wang et al. (2020) and Walker et al. (2021). By applying these methodologies, the aim was to analyse how varying assumptions, datasets, experimental setups, and methods of calculating the β factor influence the estimation of the CFE under different nutrient conditions. This will be discussed in the discussion section, as there are differences in the trends of fertilization effects using both methods below.

1. Approximation of Beta Factor Method: S. Wang et al. (2020), follows the method of comparison between global analyses and experimental observations by employing an approximate form of the original β ($\beta = \partial GPP / \partial C_a$), defined as the relative change in GPP resulting from a 100 ppm increase in atmospheric CO₂ concentration (C_a) (Bacastow & Keeling, 1973).

In S. Wang et al. (2020), the CO₂ fertilization factor (β) was estimated from the sensitivity of GPP to atmospheric CO₂ concentration using multiple linear regression within a 15-year moving window. Specifically, β was derived as the slope of GPP proxies from satellite GPP proxies (like AVHRR-NIRv, AVHRR+MODIS-NIRv, and NIRv+SIF) and other observational data were calculated using linear and nonlinear multiple regression approaches at each pixel across the globe with respect to CO₂ after accounting for concurrent variations in vapor pressure deficit (VPD) and maximum temperature (Tmax), following:

$$GPP (proxies) = \alpha + \beta_{CO_2} \Delta CO_2 + \beta_{VPD} \Delta VPD + \beta_{Tmax} \Delta Tmax + \epsilon \quad \dots(10)$$

$$\beta = \frac{\beta_{CO_2}}{\overline{GPP}} \times 100 \times 100 \quad \dots(11)$$

Where, ΔCO_2 , ΔVPD , ΔT_{max} are anomalies of CO₂, VPD, and Tmax, β_{CO_2} , β_{VPD} , β_{Tmax} are the regression residuals. \overline{GPP} is the mean GPP in the window within the 15 year window, and β expresses the relative (% per 100 ppm) change in GPP for a 100 ppm rise in CO₂.

The same conceptual framework was followed but focused solely on the GPP-CO₂ relationship because consistent meteorological drivers (VPD, Tmax) were unavailable for the region and model setup. For each 15-year rolling window and scenario, a simple linear regression was fitted between GPP and CO₂:

$$GPP = a + bCO_2 \quad \dots(11)$$

And calculated:

$$\beta = \frac{b}{\overline{GPP}} \times 100 \times 100 \quad \dots(12)$$

Equation 12 calculates β as the percent increase in GPP per 100 ppm increase in CO_2 . To examine long-term and scenario-dependent variations, β was computed separately for NLIM and UNLIM simulations under the historical (1985-2014), SSP126 (2070-2100), and SSP370 (2070-2100) scenarios, respectively, and trend statistics were derived using the Mann–Kendall and Sen’s slope tests.

2. Relativized Beta Factor Method: Walker et al. (2021) and Chen et al. (2022) compute GPP relativized by changes in CO_2 (i.e. elasticity) using the formula below:

$$\beta_{\text{in}} = (\ln \frac{GPP_e}{GPP_a}) / (\ln \frac{CO_{2,e}}{CO_{2,a}}) \quad \dots(13)$$

where GPP_a and GPP_e are the values of any response variable at lower ($\text{CO}_{2,a}$) and higher ($\text{CO}_{2,e}$), respectively. A β_{in} value of one indicates a directly proportional increase in GPP with rising CO_2 concentration. It should be noted that β_{in} is intended solely for comparative analysis; it is not a true partial derivative and therefore does not isolate the pure CO_2 effect on GPP.

For this study implementation, the same elasticity principle was followed: for each scenario (historical and SSPs), the GPP and CO_2 data were subsetted over the reporting years and fitted.

The slope of this regression is β (elasticity). To convert elasticity into a percent GPP change per +100 ppm CO_2 , the below formula was used:

$$\Delta GPP_{100} = \beta \cdot \ln \left(\frac{C_{\text{ref}} + 100}{C_{\text{ref}}} \right) \times 100 \quad \dots(14)$$

where C_{ref} is the mean CO_2 over the reporting period. This approach mirrors the β_{in} formula of Chen et al. (2022) and is consistent with the methodology used in Walker et al. (2021) elasticity regressions.

2.5.3 Random Forest model, trait importance, and dynamics

For random forest modeling analysis, the primary goal was to understand the importance of trait features in influencing productivity at the tree level in two climatically different sites, namely Santarém and Manaus, over time. The climate data inputs initially available for the entire Brazil were subsetted to the grid cells of these locations

to generate the annual tree-level output files. The simulations were performed for the historical scenarios only.

The hypothesis is that the relative importance of functional traits in predicting tree performance differs between NLIM and UNLIM conditions, with traits such as the leaf C:N ratio (leaf_cn) becoming more influential under NLIM conditions.

Random Forest is a machine learning method that constructs multiple decision trees and aggregates their outputs, it is robust to correlated predictors and nonlinear relationships (Breiman, 2001).

To prepare predictors for modeling, initially, the correlations among leaf carbon (leafc), leaf N (leafn), SLA, plant height, and wood density were examined. Leafc and leafn were found to be highly correlated (Pearson $r \approx 0.99$), which could introduce multicollinearity in further analyses. To reduce multicollinearity, the leaf carbon-to-nitrogen ratio (leaf C:N) (leaf_cn = leaf_c/leaf_n) was used instead of the individual leaf traits, resulting in near-zero correlations between leaf_cn and the other predictors (SLA, height, and wood density). The selected predictor variables include the ratio of leaf carbon to leaf N (leaf C: leaf N), SLA, wood density, and tree height, while GPP as the response variable. By selecting variables with low intercorrelation (see Figure 3), both model stability and interpretability were ensured, while reducing redundancy among predictors.

The study compares two distinct time periods: 1940-1950 and 2004-2014, to assess potential temporal shifts in predictor influence under different treatments (UNLIM and NLIM). The predictive analysis is based on an 80% training and 20% testing data split.

Figure 3: Correlation matrix of predictors selected to perform random forest modeling for the response variable GPP. The selected variables reduce the issues of multicollinearity Here, leaf_cn= leaf C:N ratio; Wooddens= Wood density; SLA=Specific Leaf Area.

The random forest algorithm was implemented for the large trees (height \geq 10 metres) and small trees (5 metres \leq height $<$ 10 metres) for the following settings:

Table 2: Overview of experiment settings for random forest modeling for large and small trees, where NLIM is the N-limited case, and UNLIM is the N-unlimited case. R² values show the importance of tree type in predicting the GPP values.

Site	Treatment	Analysis Decades	R ² value for Large Trees selected variables	R ² value for Small Trees selected variables
Manaus	NLIM	1940-1950	0.50	0.14
		2004-2014	0.40	0.09
	UNLIM	1940-1950	0.46	0.23
		2004-2014	0.35	0.08
Santarém	NLIM	1940-1950	0.50	0.18
		2004-2014	0.59	0.21
	UNLIM	1940-1950	0.49	0.18
		2004-2014	0.54	0.20

Although further analysis was conducted on only large trees, as the preliminary model results showed very low R² values (see Table 3), indicating that the selected traits from small trees had a negligible effect on predicting GPP values in the regions.

2.5.4 Plant Trait Trade-Off Analysis

The relationship between SLA and LNC was analyzed using outputs from the LPJmL-FIT model and observational data obtained from the TRY plant trait database. This analysis aimed to evaluate how well the model reproduces the empirical relationship observed in global vegetation datasets.

SLA represents the ratio of leaf area to leaf dry mass and serves as an indicator of leaf thickness and structural investment, (Poorter et al., 2009; Wright et al., 2004), expressed as:

$$SLA(m^2 g^{-1} C^{-1}) = \frac{Leaf\ area\ (m^2)}{Leaf\ dry\ mass\ (gC)} \quad \dots(15)$$

LNC was expressed on a dry-mass basis (g N g⁻¹ or % N). But global trait studies have shown that LNC per leaf area and SLA are approximately log-normally distributed and negatively correlated (Poorter & Evans, 1998; Reich et al., 1997; Westoby et al., 2000;

Wright et al., 2004). The empirical relationship is typically represented as a power-law (log-log) relationship.

For mechanistic or simpler linear approximations, some studies have expressed LNC as a linear function of SLA:

$$LMA = \frac{1}{SLA} \quad \dots(16)$$

; and hence

$$LNC = a + \frac{b}{LMA} \text{ (Poorter et al., 2009)} \quad \dots(17)$$

In the LPJmL-FIT model, SLA and leaf N traits are parameterized based on PFT-specific relationships (Sakschewski et al., 2015).

To ensure consistency with the TRY database, model outputs were post-processed to derive comparable variables using the following transformations:

$$Leaf\ area\ (m^2) = SLA\ (m^2g^{-1}C^{-1}) * leafC(gC) \quad \dots(18)$$

Where the units of SLA are changed, using below conversion:

$$SLA(mm^2mg^{-1}) = SLA(m^2g^{-1}C^{-1}) \times 1000 \times 0.455gC \quad \dots(19)$$

where, 0.455 gC is equal to 1 g of biomass, LNC can be re-written as:

$$LNC = \frac{leafN}{Leaf\ area\ (m^2)} = \frac{leafN}{SLA \times leafC} \quad \dots(21)$$

where *leafC* and *leafN* in grams (g) represent the model-simulated leaf carbon and N content, respectively.

The empirical observations dataset of around 4797 tree species for SLA without petiole (TRY traitID=3115) in mm²mg⁻¹ and LNC per leaf area (TRY traitID=50) in g m⁻² was downloaded from the TRY website (Kattge et al., 2020).

For both the TRY database and LPJmL-FIT simulations, a log-log regression was applied to quantify the scaling relationship between SLA and LNC, described as:

$$\log(LNC) = a + b * \log(SLA) \quad \dots(22)$$

where a and b denote the intercept and slope, respectively, describing the strength and direction of the relationship between these two leaf traits (Reich et al., 1998; Wright et al., 2004).

In the absence of site-specific trait data for Santarém and Manaus within the TRY database, the analysis was limited to 1,480 broad-leaved evergreen species. This filtering ensured consistency with the tropical PFT represented in the LPJmL-FIT model for the log-log SLA-LNC comparison.

The slope parameter (b) obtained from the TRY data was compared to the slopes derived from LPJmL-FIT outputs for Manaus and Santarém, two Amazon sites that differ in environmental conditions (temperature, precipitation) (see Supplementary Figures 31,32). This comparison was used to assess the model's ability to reproduce observed patterns in the SLA-LNC relationship and to evaluate the consistency of trait scaling between empirical observations and model simulations.

3. Results

This chapter presents the main outputs of model simulations and the analyses to represent the differences between the NLIM and UNLIM factorial experiments under different climate change scenarios. Firstly, the influence of nitrogen limitation on biomass and productivity is analysed (section 3.1), followed by a spatial and temporal analysis at the biome level (section 3.2), a sensitivity analysis of the biological nitrogen fixation (section 3.3), the investigation of the CO₂ fertilization effect (section 3.4), the plant trait analysis (section 3.6), and finally including their trade-offs (section 3.7).

3.1 Influence of Nitrogen Limitation on Biomass and Vegetation Productivity

The simulated GPP indicates strong historical increases from 1850 to 2014 across the study area, with conditions generally producing a slightly higher mean GPP by 9 % depicted by Sen's slope values in Figure 4 for GPP were strong (0.025 PgC yr⁻¹ for under unlimited conditions than under N-limited conditions. Historical trend rates UNLIM vs. 0.023 PgC yr⁻¹ for NLIM), and VegC increased even more sharply (0.191

PgC yr⁻¹ for UNLIM vs. 0.145 PgC yr⁻¹ for NLIM) (Supplementary Figure 24). Future projections from the years 2015-2100 vary depending on the emission scenario, where increases under SSP126 are moderate: VegC grows more under unlimited N conditions (0.302 PgC yr⁻¹) vs. 0.174 PgC yr⁻¹ under N limitation (see Supplementary Figure 24), while N-limited GPP (0.013 PgC yr⁻¹) surpasses unlimited N conditions (0.007 PgC yr⁻¹) (Figure 5). SSP370 projects large gains in both variables, with unlimited GPP (0.092 PgC yr⁻¹, see Figure 6) and VegC (1.160 PgC yr⁻¹, see Supplementary Figure 24) rising significantly higher than their N-limited results (0.070 PgC yr⁻¹ for GPP and 0.637 for VegC PgC yr⁻¹, respectively). N limitation consistently reduces carbon storage (VegC) and productivity (GPP, NPP), and alters vegetation structure under both historical (1985-2014; Supplementary Table 5) and future scenarios (2015-2100; Supplementary Table 6 for SSP126 and Supplementary Table 7 for SSP370). VegC has historically been 7% lower under N limitation (44 GtC) than in the unlimited case (47 GtC), and decreases in NPP (-12%), GPP (-10%), and transpiration (-16%) are also noticeable (Supplementary Table 5).

Figure 4: Historical absolute GPP simulated by LPJmL-FIT under limited nitrogen (NLIM) (black solid line) and unlimited nitrogen (UNLIM) (blue solid line) conditions in Brazil. In both factorial experiments, the trend (black dashed line for NLIM and blue dashed line for UNLIM) is statistically significant (p -value <0.05), whereas the trend increases over time by 0.025 PgC/yr in the unlimited and by 0.023PgC/yr in the limited case using Sen's slope.

Figure 5: SSP126 absolute GPP simulated by LPJmL-FIT under limited nitrogen (NLIM) (black solid line) and unlimited nitrogen (UNLIM) (blue solid line) conditions in Brazil. In both factorial experiments, the trend (black dashed line for NLIM and blue dashed line for UNLIM) is statistically significant (p -value <0.05), whereas the trend increases over time by 0.007 PgC/yr in the unlimited and by 0.013PgC/yr in the limited case using Sen's slope.

Figure 6: SSP370 absolute GPP simulated by LPJmL-FIT under limited nitrogen (NLIM) (black solid line) and unlimited nitrogen (UNLIM) (blue solid line) conditions in Brazil. In both factorial experiments, the trend (black dashed line for NLIM and blue dashed line for UNLIM) is statistically significant (p -value <0.05), whereas the trend increases over time by 0.092 PgC/yr in the unlimited and by 0.07PgC/yr in the limited case using Sen's slope.

The structural changes include expansions of temperate needle-leaved evergreen trees (+22%) and tropical C4 grasses (+30%), while decreases in tropical evergreen broad-leaved trees (-5%) and temperate summergreen broad-leaved trees (-52%). Under the low-emission future scenario (SSP126), these effects become more pronounced: VegC drops by 16% (from 60 GtC to 51 GtC), with similar reductions in NPP (-12%), GPP (-10%), and transpiration (-14%). Vegetation composition shifts in the same direction, with further loss of tropical evergreen broad-leaved trees (-12%) and summergreen broad-leaved trees (-47%), while needle-leaved evergreen trees (+27%) and C4 grasses (+44–46%) expand (see Supplementary Table 6). N limitation has the greatest impact in the high-emission scenario (SSP370), lowering VegC by almost 19% (-13 GtC) and decreasing NPP (-14%), GPP (-13%), and transpiration (-16%). The changes in vegetation composition are also more pronounced, with summergreen broad-leaved trees (-47%) and tropical evergreen forests (-13%) experiencing significant declines, while needle-leaved evergreen trees (+27%) and C4 grasses (+46%) continue to grow (see Supplementary Table 7).

Figures 7 and 8 show that the N limitation has had a minimal impact on VegC over the pre-acceleration period (before the year 1950) (Steffen et al., 2015); the ratio of limited to unlimited results is close to 1, and the difference between unlimited and N-limited vegetation carbon is negligible, at approximately 0%.

Figure 7: Difference percentage trends (blue) between UNLIM and NLIM values of vegetation carbon (VegC) over the years for the scenarios: historical, SSP126, and SSP370 w.r.t percentage change in carbon dioxide (secondary axis=red dashed lines) for the scenarios. The percentage represents the difference between UNLIM and NLIM values, increasing with the percentage change in CO₂ over time.

By 2015, in the post-1950 acceleration period (Steffen et al., 2015), the N limitation is more noticeable: the ratio drops to 0.86, and the percentage difference reaches about

14%. N limitation increases moderately under SSP126, with the ratio dropping to 0.77 and the difference increasing to roughly 23% by the middle of the century, after which both metrics level off.

Figure 8: Ratio of NLIM and UNLIM (blue solid line) VegC w.r.t increasing CO₂ (secondary axis=red dashed line) for the three scenarios: historical (upper panel), SSP126 (middle panel), and SSP370 (lower panel). The ratio shows a decrease in VegC values under the NLIM condition over the years with increasing CO₂.

On the other hand, the limitation worsens more quickly under SSP370: by mid-century, the difference rises to about 25% (see Figure 7; scenario SSP370), and the ratio falls

Figure 9: Difference percentage trends (blue) between UNLIM and NLIM values of gross primary productivity (GPP) over the years for the scenarios: historical, SSP126, and SSP370 w.r.t percentage change in carbon dioxide (secondary axis=red dashed lines) for the scenarios. The percentage shows the difference between UNLIM and NLIM values, with the percentage change in CO₂ over the years.

to 75% (see Figure 8; scenario SSP370) before continuing to decline, indicating greater constraints on vegetation carbon under high-emission scenarios. Although the amount and pattern differ, N limitation always lowers GPP in comparison to unlimited conditions in all three scenarios, as seen in Figures 9 and 10. Both climate variability and rising CO₂ are reflected in the historical period (1850–2014), where the N-limited to unlimited GPP ratio varies between approximately 0.85 and 0.95, with GPP differences ranging from 6 to 14%. The ratio steadily decreases to approximately 0.87–0.88 under the moderate-emissions SSP126 scenario (2015–2100), with GPP differences primarily falling between 11 and 14%. This suggests a moderate yet consistent suppression of GPP as CO₂ levels increase. While GPP differences rise to 12–15% in the high-emissions SSP370 scenario, the ratio similarly begins near 0.89–0.90 but exhibits a slight long-term decline, highlighting the strongest N limitation effect due to amplified CO₂ fertilization potential.

Figure 10: Ratio of gross primary productivity (GPP) for NLIM and UNLIM (blue solid line) w.r.t increasing carbon dioxide (secondary axis=red dashed line) for the three scenarios: historical (upper panel), SSP126 (middle panel), and SSP370 (lower panel). The ratio shows decrease in VegC values under NLIM condition over the years w.r.t. increasing CO₂.

3.2 Spatial and Temporal Analysis of Biomes for Brazil

Although the extent of the effect varies by biome, the mean GPP values for Brazil's biomes demonstrate that N limitation lowers GPP across all major Brazilian biomes

Figure 11: Projected mean GPP in $\text{gC/m}^2/\text{month}$ for UNLIM and NLIM cases for the three scenarios: Historical (1850-2014) (upper row panel), SSP126 (2015-2100) (middle row panel), and SSP370 (2015-2100) (lower row panel) for different biomes of Brazil. Green color denotes high GPP, while yellow and red color shows low GPP values.

and scenarios (see Figure 11). The highest mean monthly GPP during the historical period (1850-2014) is found in Amazon and Mata Atlântica under UNLIM conditions, at about $166\text{-}167 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$. Under NLIM, it implies a monthly GPP drop to $146\text{-}156 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$, indicating a significant reduction of approximately 7-12%. The decrease is somewhat less pronounced in drier areas such as Caatinga and Cerrado, where GPP drops from $158\text{-}114 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$ to $143\text{-}116 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$. With Amazon reaching $215 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$ and Pampa reaching $210 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$, all biomes exhibit a clear increase in GPP under UNLIM under the moderate-emissions

SSP126 (2015-2100) scenario. For SSP370 (2015-2100) Amazonia peaking at $241 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$ under UNLIM and falling to $202 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$ under NLIM. Cerrado and Mata Atlântica exhibit comparable trends.

Figure 12: Mean projected GPP difference in $\text{gC/m}^2/\text{month}$ between NLIM and UNLIM cases for three scenarios: a) Historical (1850-2014) (1st panel), b) SSP126 (2015-2100) (2nd panel), and c) SSP370 (2015-2100) (3rd panel) for different biomes in Brazil. Blue color denotes high NLIM values, while light red means high UNLIM values and white means no to very small difference.

Across all scenarios, NLIM conditions generally reduced values compared to UNLIM simulations, indicating consistent nutrient constraints on productivity (see Figure 12). Under historical climate conditions, most biomes showed moderate reductions, with the strongest reductions in the Amazon ($-19.7 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$) and Cerrado ($-16.2 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$), while the Caatinga experienced a slight increase ($+2.3 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$). Under SSP126, all biomes declined, with the largest differences in the Amazon ($-29.2 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$) and Cerrado ($-20.6 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$). The SSP370 scenario amplified these effects, with the Amazon ($-38.8 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$) and Cerrado ($-28.1 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$) again showing the highest sensitivity. Overall, nutrient limitation intensified from Historical to SSP126 and SSP370, particularly affecting tropical and savanna biomes.

3.3 Constraining the CO₂ Fertilization Effects

The constant-CO₂ sensitivity run (atmospheric CO₂ concentration fixed at 1901 levels) allows us to isolate CO₂-driven effects from climate change. In Figure 13 (A), for most of the historical period, GPP in NLIM scenarios closely resembles the constant-CO₂ baseline, with slight increases over time (~16% by 2014), underscoring the function of CO₂ fertilization. The combined effects of rising CO₂ are reflected in UNLIM scenarios, where GPP deviates more from the baseline and is over 21% higher than in the constant-CO₂ experiment by 2014 (see Figure 14). This comparison reveals that CO₂

Figure 13: Projected GPP (panel A) and VegC (panel B) trends in PgC/yr for the historical scenario (1850-2014) for both UNLIM and NLIM cases under fixed (dashed lines- purple=UNLIM, yellow=NLIM) and dynamic (solid lines- blue=UNLIM, green=NLIM) CO₂ concentration supply in the simulations. The influence of CO₂ can be clearly seen in the increasing trend of both UNLIM and NLIM outputs.

enrichment is primarily responsible for the majority of GPP enhancement in historical simulations.

Figure 14: Difference in GPP [in%] between dynamic and fixed CO₂ concentration case for UNLIM (blue solid line), and for NLIM (green solid line). Both are computed as a percentage change of dynamic GPP – fixed GPP.

Likewise, in N-limited conditions, VegC closely resembles the constant-CO₂ runs, with only slight deviations ($\Delta\text{VEGC_NLIM}$ ~26 PgC by 2014). On the other hand, under unlimited N scenarios, VegC deviates increasingly from the constant-CO₂ trajectory; by 2014, the difference ($\Delta\text{VEGC_UNLIM}$) had increased from slightly negative values in the 19th century to nearly 37 PgC (see Figure 13 B).

3.4 Sensitivity Analysis of BNF Ratios

The effect of varying plant BNF rates on the GPP values varied under all climate scenarios (historical 1985-2014, SSP126, and SSP370 (2015-2100)) for different BNF ratios (see Figure 15). Baseline GPP continuously falls between the doubled and halved BNF cases in all scenarios, demonstrating the ongoing significance of N availability in controlling carbon uptake. Prior medians were approximately 15 PgC yr⁻¹, but they increased to approximately 19 PgC yr⁻¹ in SSP126 and approximately 21 PgC yr⁻¹ in SSP370. Under SSP370, there is the greatest difference between doubled and halved cases, suggesting that N limitation effects will be more pronounced in a future with high emissions.

Figure 15: Boxplot of projected GPP values for BNF ratios being doubled (green), halved (blue), and kept at baseline (red) in PgC/yr for three scenarios: Historical (1st panel), SSP126 (2nd panel), and SSP370 (3rd panel).

3.5 Carbon Fertilization Effect (CFE) Analysis

This chapter presents the results of the CFE analysis, which utilized the computed beta factor (see Section 2.5.2 for detailed methods).

3.5.1 Rolling-Window Approach

Following the methods of S. Wang et al. (2020) in the historical period from 1985 to 2014, β declined significantly for both nutrient treatment cases ($\tau = -0.63$ to -0.73 , $p < 0.001$), with median values dropping from $\sim 25\%$ per 100 ppm CO_2 in 1982–1996 to 13% (NLIM) and 17% (UNLIM) in 2001–2014 (see Figure 16, Historical). Under SSP126 from 2070 to 2100, β trends diverged: the increase was not significant for NLIM (median $\sim 13\text{--}14\%$), but UNLIM showed a significant rise ($\tau = 0.54$, $p = 0.003$; median $\sim 17\text{--}21\%$) (see Figure 16, SSP126). In contrast, SSP370 from 2070 to 2100 exhibited significant declines in both cases ($\tau = -0.46$ to -0.51 , $p < 0.05$), with medians falling to $\sim 11\text{--}15\%$ (see Figure 16, SSP370). Together, these results suggest a strong historical weakening of CFE, partial recovery only under low-emission pathways, and continued decline under high-emission scenarios.

Figure 16: Temporal dynamics of β for GPP in NLIM (red solid line) and UNLIM (blue solid line) shown as 15-year moving windows for 3 scenarios: Historical (1985 to 2014) (panel A), SSP126 (2070-2100) (panel B), and SSP370 (2070-2100) (panel C). The $\tau(t)$ and Sen's slope were estimated using the Mann-Kendall and Sen's slope tests; see the test statistics in each panel. (All trends are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$)).

3.5.2 Relativized β -factor Analysis

From the β elasticity calculation (see section 2.5.2.2 for detailed methodology), across scenarios, a strong contrast in the CO₂ fertilization effect (β) was found. During the historical period (1985–2014, C_{ref}≈369 ppm), β was 0.61 under UNLIM and 0.50 under NLIM, corresponding to a GPP increase of 14.6% and 12.0% per 100 ppm CO₂, respectively. Under the low-emission scenario SSP126 (C_{ref}≈461 ppm), β values rose to 0.95 (UNLIM) and 0.93 (NLIM), yielding similar Δ GPP₁₀₀ responses of 18.7% and 18.2%, respectively. In contrast, under the high-emission scenario SSP370 (C_{ref}≈754 ppm), β declined sharply to ~0.09, with Δ GPP₁₀₀ reduced to only ~1% regardless of N status.

Table 3 : CO₂ fertilization sensitivity (β) and percent change in GPP (Δ GPP) for a +100-ppm increase in CO₂ in Brazil under unlimited N (UNLIM) and limited N (NLIM).

Scenario	Reference CO ₂ (ppm)	β (UNLIM)	β (NLIM)	Δ GPP per +100 ppm CO ₂ (%) UNLIM	Δ GPP per +100 ppm CO ₂ (%) NLIM
Historical	369	0.61	0.50	14.6	12.0
SSP126	461	0.95	0.93	18.7	18.2
SSP370	754	0.09	0.09	1.16	1.11

3.6 Significance of Plant-traits using Random Forest Model Analysis

To understand the importance and changes in various plant traits that contribute to productivity (GPP), an advanced machine learning technique, random forest analysis, is employed in this section for the two Amazon sites: Santarém and Manaus.

3.6.1 Plant Trait Importance

Firstly, to understand plant-traits influencing GPP for different decades, the percentage of Mean Squared Error (%MSE), also known as feature importance, is analysed. Feature importance means how much a variable matters for the model's prediction (magnitude); it does not state whether the effect is positive or negative. Therefore, if a particular trait has a higher percentage of MSE, it means that excluding this trait from the model would result in a higher error in predicting GPP values; in other words, the trait has a higher feature importance in contributing to the predictions.

For large trees at Santarém Figure 17, random Forest feature importance indicated that, under unlimited N, structural traits were the dominant predictors of GPP, with height and wood density showing the highest values in both the 1940-1950 and 2004-2014 periods. Their importance increased over time (height: 411.67 to 433.70; wood density: 256.76 to 301.47), while leaf C:N decreased slightly (104.70 to 83.25). Under N limitation, leaf traits gained importance, with leaf C:N and SLA increasing from 152.84 to 178.04 and 98.86 to 119.89, respectively, whereas height and wood density also rose but remained lower than in the unlimited N case.

Figure 17: Percentage increase in Mean Squared Error (%MSE) from random forest model showing feature importance for UNLIM (blue bars) and NLIM (orange bars) cases for Santarém site. The features' importance is determined for two decades: 1. Pre-acceleration time (1940-1950), 2. Post-acceleration time (2004-2014). Here: leaf_cn = Leaf C:N ratio; SLA= Specific Leaf Area; Wooddens= Wood density.

Similarly, at Manaus Figure 18, feature importance for large trees shows overall lower values compared to Santarém and declined between 1940–1950 and 2004–2014 across all traits. Under unlimited N, height (243.45 to 133.23) and wood density (changing from 225.49 to 132.59) were the leading predictors initially, but lost importance over time, as did SLA (from 91.39 to 62.06) and leaf C:N (from 68.62 to 66.34). Under N limitation, a similar decline was observed, with leaf C:N (from 118.01 to 67.90), SLA (from 109.18 to 67.92), height (from 209.93 to 115.77), and wood density (from 198.70 to 90.58), meaning that all traits were decreasing in their predictive importance.

Figure 18: Percentage increase in Mean Squared Error (%MSE) from random forest model showing feature importance for UNLIM (blue bars) and NLIM (orange bars) cases for Manaus study site. The features' importance is determined for two decades: 1. Pre-acceleration time (1940-1950), 2. Post-acceleration time (2004-2014). Here: leaf_cn = Leaf C:N ratio; SLA= Specific Leaf Area; Wooddens= Wood density.

3.6.2 Contribution of Plant Traits using SHAPLEY values

To improve the interpretability of random forest predictions, Shap values were included in the analysis and plotted in beeswarm figures. Shapley values (ϕ) give a local, direction-specific contribution for the observed feature value (whether that state increases or decreases predicted GPP). So, a trait can be highly important overall, but maybe contribute to GPP reductions.

The SHAP beeswarm plots in Figure 19 for Santarém's large trees (2004-2014) provide a clear visual narrative of how N availability alters the mechanistic drivers of GPP. In the UNLIM scenario, the plot reveals height as the dominant feature, with a stark pattern of high values (red dots) more spread out, exerting a strong positive impact on model output. The most telling contrast is evident in the leaf_cn (C:N ratio) feature, where its values are scattered widely but cluster tightly around a SHAP value of zero, indicating that it has no consistent directional impact when N is unlimited. This null effect collapses entirely in the NLIM scenario. Here, leaf C:N reveals a powerful and consistent negative relationship, with high values (red dots) strongly suppressing the predicted GPP. This dramatic emergence of a clear pattern for leaf_cn in the NLIM plot visually captures the essence of N limitation, showing how it becomes a central,

constraining mechanism on productivity, a finding that is quantitatively reinforced by its more than doubled %IncMSE importance value.

Figure 19: SHAP values for Santarém features for large trees for the years 2004–2014, where A) is the UNLIM case (left panel) and B) is the NLIM case (right panel). Each panel illustrates the marginal contribution (SHAP value, x-axis) of the four selected structural and foliar traits (y-axis) to the model's prediction of GPP. The Feature Value (color scale) indicates the trait's actual magnitude, ranging from low (blue) to high (red). Features plotted on the positive x-axis (right) increase predicted GPP. The compact clustering of all feature points near the zero axis in both the UNLIM and NLIM cases demonstrates the weak and diminished predictive importance of these classic traits for large-tree productivity in Santarém during this period.

Figure 20: SHAP values for Manaus features for large trees for the years 2004–2014, where A) is the UNLIM case (left panel) and B) is the NLIM case (right panel). Each panel illustrates the marginal contribution (SHAP value, x-axis) of the four selected structural and foliar traits (y-axis) to the model's prediction of GPP. The Feature Value (color scale) indicates the trait's actual magnitude, ranging from low (blue) to high (red). Features plotted on the positive x-axis (right) increase predicted GPP. The compact clustering of all feature points near the zero axis in both the UNLIM and NLIM cases demonstrates the weak and diminished predictive importance of these classic traits for large-tree productivity in Manaus during this period.

For Manaus' large trees (2004-2014), Figure 20 reveals a system predominantly driven by canopy structure (Height), with functional traits playing a minimal role. Crucially, and in direct contrast to Santarém, the leaf C:N feature exhibits no consistent pattern in either the NLIM or UNLIM scenario, with its values clustered tightly around a SHAP value of zero. This visual evidence suggests that N availability, as indicated by leaf C:N, is not a primary constraint on productivity for these trees. This finding is robustly supported by the %IncMSE values, which show that the importance of leaf_cn remains unchanged and low between scenarios.

3.7 Trade-off Analysis between SLA and LNC

The log–log regression between LNC and SLA reveals a consistently negative relationship, with both the global TRY observations and the LPJmL-FIT model simulations showing an inverse scaling between the two traits.

Table 4: Log-log regression slope value results between SLA and LNC values of the TRY dataset and LPJmL-FIT results for Santarém and Manaus study sites (UNLIM and NLIM cases).

Dataset	Location	Slope between LNC and SLA
TRY	Global	-0.622
TRY	Global (Evergreen Broadleaved Trees)	-0.624
LPJmL-FIT	Santarém UNLIM	-1.27
LPJmL-FIT	Santarém NLIM	-1.31
LPJmL-FIT	Manaus-UNLIM	-1.26
LPJmL-FIT	Manaus-NLIM	-1.34

Across the global TRY dataset, a slope of -0.622 was found (see Figure 21), which is very similar to the value obtained for evergreen broadleaved trees (-0.624). Figures 22 and 23 show that, the LPJmL-FIT simulations produced steeper slopes at the tropical forest sites. In Santarém, the slope was -1.27 under unlimited nutrient supply and -1.31 under nutrient limitation. In Manaus, similarly steep slopes -1.26 and -1.34 were found for UNLIM and NLIM, respectively. This comparison indicates that the LPJmL-FIT model tends to overestimate the strength of the negative LNC-SLA relationship relative to the TRY database. In other words, the simulated decrease in

leaf N content with increasing SLA is much stronger in the LPJmL-FIT model than the documented TRY database.

Figure 21: TRY database Log-log regression plot between LNC in g/m² and SLA in mm²/mg for A) only broadleaved-evergreen trees of around 1480 species, B) the global dataset of 4797 tree species. The blue points are the individual LNC and SLA values, and the solid red line is the slope between the two.

Figure 22: LPJmL-FIT output Log-log regression plot for Santarém between LNC in g/m² and SLA in mm²/mg for A) NLIM case, B) UNLIM case. Each green point shows the SLA and LNC trait value combination of an individual tree, whereas the solid blue line is the slope between the two parameters.

Furthermore, the temporal heat density plots (see Supplementary Figures 29 and 30) of SLA and LNC show that SLA increases gradually across the simulation period, while LNC decreases in parallel. The decline in LNC is more pronounced under nutrient limitation, underscoring the greater sensitivity of N allocation to resource constraints. These modelled temporal dynamics not only reinforce the negative SLA–

LNC scaling but also highlight how resource constraints shape long-term leaf trait trajectories in tropical forests.

Figure 23: LPJmL-FIT output Log-log regression plot for Manaus between LNC in g/m^2 and SLA in mm^2/mg for A) NLIM case, B) UNLIM case. Each green point shows the SLA and LNC trait value combination of an individual tree, whereas the solid blue line is the slope between the two parameters.

4. Discussion

This thesis evaluated how nitrogen limitation affects carbon cycling and plant productivity across Brazil's major biomes using simulations from the LPJmL-FIT model. The results are discussed below in relation to earlier studies, the modeling approach used, and the key uncertainties of the analysis.

4.1 Nitrogen Constraints on Carbon Uptake in Tropical Ecosystems

Nitrogen availability has been a key constraint on the carbon dynamics of Brazilian ecosystems in the LPJmL-FIT model simulations of this study.

The general trend results of GPP (Figures 4, 5, 6) and VegC (Supplementary Figure 24) from the model simulations indicate a decline in output values for the N-limited case compared to the unlimited N case. These declining trends are also observed in several other studies of tropical forests or N limitations (He et al., 2017; LeBauer & Treseder, 2008; Lee et al., 2013; Reich & Hobbie, 2013; Wieder et al., 2015).

The historical reductions (1985-2014) showing NPP decreased by 12% and GPP decreased by 10% due to N limitation align with the broad consensus that C-only models exaggerate the terrestrial biosphere's potential to accumulate carbon (see

Supplementary Table 5). In the tropical context, the BEPS model, using a satellite-derived proxy for photosynthetic N content (MTCI), confirmed this limitation, finding extensive GPP decreasing trends in tropical forests (especially in South American Evergreen broadleaf forest, around $-19.0 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) as when N constraint was included (He et al., 2017). Furthermore, the future simulations were more constrained, with future VegC dropping by 16–19% and NPP by 12–14% under SSP126 and SSP370, respectively (see Supplementary Table 6 and 7), directly support the concept of Progressive N Limitation (Luo et al., 2004; Smith et al., 2014; Thornton et al., 2009).

The reductions in GPP, NPP, VegC in the results is also consistent with the findings from CLM-CN model, which simulated a profound 62% increase in NPP in humid tropical forests following N fertilization (Thomas et al., 2013). However, these results contrasts with other models, like O-CN (Zaehle et al., 2010) and JULES-CN (Wiltshire et al., 2021), which predicted that N dynamics have a lower importance for tropical C exchange, suggesting instead that productivity might be primarily limited by P in these regions . Even if tropical GPP is not strongly N-limited under contemporary conditions, as suggested by CN-TEM (Sokolov et al., 2008), N constraints will likely increase as elevated atmospheric CO_2 drives higher N demand that cannot be met by mineralization rates (Zaehle et al., 2010).

The 16 %decrease in transpiration for historical scenario (see Supplementary Table 5) highlights the link between N limitation and tropical water cycling, consistent with ORCHIDEE simulations where including C-N interactions reduced transpiration by $\sim 50 \text{ mm yr}^{-1}$ alongside suppressed carbon productivity (Vuichard et al., 2019).

N limitation had a rather low effect on VegC during the pre-1950 period, but became increasingly important toward the present and under future projections. The increased VegC reduction by 2015 ($\sim 14\%$) (see Supplementary Figure 24) corresponds with the onset of stronger N constraints under elevated CO_2 , as also reported by other model simulations (Gerber et al., 2010; Thornton et al., 2007). This gap widened under future scenarios, reaching $\sim 23\%$ in SSP126 and $\sim 25\%$ in SSP370 (see Supplementary Figure 24).

The model FPC differences between UNLIM and NLIM results reveal declines in tropical broadleaved evergreen trees and summergreen species, accompanied by expansions of needle-leaved evergreens and C_4 grasses (see Supplementary Figures

26, 27, and 28). There is a 5% drop in tropical evergreen broad-leaved trees when N is limited, showing that a lack of N directly reduces carbon storage in these high-biomass forests. This also shows that models need to account for local differences in N availability, like ORCHIDEE (version r8849), which had to adjust N use efficiency in different parts of the Amazon to accurately match observed biomass and productivity (L. Zhu et al., 2025).

N limitation influences carbon dynamics through both physiological and structural mechanisms. Physiologically, limited N reduces photosynthetic capacity and leaf area development, thereby constraining carbon assimilation, which explains the consistently lower GPP (Mu & Chen, 2021).

Similarly, a study done by Lapola et al. (2009) using the CPTEC-PVM2 PNV model shows that CO₂ fertilization and dry season length strongly control South American biomes, with weak fertilization or longer dry seasons driving Amazon forests toward savanna or shrubland states.

These changes in plant functional types reduce carbon storage and also alter key ecosystem processes, including evapotranspiration and carbon residence time (Bonan, 2008; Smith et al., 2014).

4.2 Spatio-Temporal Dynamics of Productivity and Carbon Storage under Nutrient Limitations

Across all major Brazilian biomes and climate scenarios, N limitation significantly decreases the GPP in this study simulations. Although the magnitude varied among biomes and scenarios. The largest N-driven reductions occur in the Amazon and Cerrado regions, while the Caatinga shows only a small historical difference that becomes negative under future scenarios (see Figures 11, 12). But, the overall pattern supports the understanding that N limitation restricts productivity in most ecosystems, and the extent of this limitation differs across biomes (LeBauer & Treseder, 2008).

The modeled reductions in GPP under N limitation align with numerous empirical studies demonstrating that N scarcity constrains ecosystem functioning across Brazil's biomes. N manipulations and N-cycle studies conducted by Bustamante et al. (2012a), Silveira et al. (2021), and Winbourne et al. (2018) in the Mata Atlântica and Cerrado

demonstrate detectable responses of plant growth and soil processes to N additions or changes in N cycling.

Additionally, evidence of high biological N fixation in wetland and seasonally flooded systems, such as the Pantanal (Reis et al., 2020), may help explain the smaller relative NLIM–UNLIM differences observed in some regions.

In this thesis, in the Amazon tropical forests, the absolute GPP declines were observed under N limitation. But the field studies found that P, rather than N alone, often limits productivity in Amazon ecosystems (Fleischer et al., 2019; Cunha et al., 2022; Lugli et al., 2024).

The dry Cerrado biome exhibited strong N limitation effects, with GPP declines of up to $-28.1 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ month}^{-1}$ under the SSP370 scenario. These results align with experimental and observational studies finding that productivity in the Cerrado is limited by intensified nutrient losses due to seasonal water stress with reduced rainfall, enhanced seasonality, and disrupted nutrient coupling between N and P. These processes make the Cerrado vulnerable to climate-induced drying and increased fire frequency, potentially shifting it from a carbon sink to a carbon source under future conditions (Bustamante et al., 2012b; Da Lacerda et al., 2024).

In the semi-arid Caatinga, differences between NLIM and UNLIM were small in the historical period but increased in future scenarios in the results. This finding aligns with the study showing that productivity in Caatinga is mainly constrained by water availability rather than nutrient supply (Costa et al., 2022).

Overall, the study findings show that N limits plant growth across all Brazilian biomes, though the strength of this effect varies with water, soil, and vegetation conditions. As the climate gets warmer and drier, these nutrient and water shortages are likely to work together to reduce carbon uptake, making many ecosystems more vulnerable to future change.

4.3 Rising CO₂ and Nitrogen Availability Effects on Ecosystem Productivity

The constant-CO₂ sensitivity experiment, in which atmospheric CO₂ concentrations were fixed at 1901 levels, provided an understanding to disentangle the effects of CO₂

enrichment from those of climate variability on terrestrial productivity (see Figure 13). Until 1901, the trends for GPP and VegC were the same for both dynamic and constant CO₂ cases. Post 1901, the dynamic CO₂ result trends started rising, suggesting that the observed rise in GPP during the 20th century is mainly related to atmospheric CO₂ enhancement (Ainsworth & Long, 2005; Zaehle et al., 2010). In contrast, simulations assuming unlimited N availability show a substantial divergence from the fixed-CO₂ baseline, highlighting that the strength of the CO₂ fertilization effect is related to rising CO₂ concentrations, which is strongly constrained in the NLIM case due to nutrient limitations in the model, as also supported by the synthesis of evidence in the review by Walker et al. (2021), and Wieder et al. (2015).

In the results, even under the constant CO₂ and NLIM conditions, productivity is still, highlighting the importance of the C-N cycle (Hungate et al., 2003; Thornton et al., 2007). Projections that omit these processes risk overestimating terrestrial carbon uptake and the long-term strength of the land carbon sink under future climate scenarios (Wieder et al., 2015; Zaehle & Dalmonech, 2011).

Across all climate scenarios, GPP increased with higher BNF and declined when BNF was reduced (see Figure 15). For SSP370, the median GPP gap among BNF scenarios was the highest, indicating that BNF influences productivity in tropical forests due to the tight coupling between C and N cycles (Davies-Barnard et al., 2022).

BNF enables primary productivity and works as a critical function in regulating human-driven alterations to global N and carbon cycles, representing the dominant natural input of external N to unmanaged ecosystems (Reis et al., 2020; Sullivan et al., 2014). In the tropics, biological nitrogen fixation is a key source of nitrogen, replacing nutrients that are lost from soils through leaching and denitrification (Cleveland et al., 1999; Cusack et al., 2009; Sullivan et al., 2014). Variability in biological fixation rates, driven by temperature, moisture, and vegetation composition, can thus substantially alter the balance between carbon assimilation and nutrient availability (Reed et al., 2011; Vitousek et al., 2013). Tropical rainforests previously assumed to have highest BNF rates on earth are found to have lower rates by various empirical data and model studies (Reis et al., 2020; Sullivan et al., 2014). Uncertainty and a lack of empirical

datasets of BNF rates in the vegetation models overestimate the net productivity of these forests (Davies-Barnard et al., 2022).

Overall, these findings indicate that both rising CO₂ levels and increased N availability through BNF have an impact on the forest's productivity.

4.4 Trait-Based Mechanisms of Productivity under Nitrogen Limitation

At Santarém, random forest analysis results show that under UNLIM conditions, structural traits, particularly height and wood density, were consistently the dominant predictors of GPP for large trees in both 1940-1950 and 2004-2014, and their importance increased over time (see Figure 17). In contrast, leaf C:N declined slightly. This pattern suggests that when N is not a limiting factor, canopy structure and carbon investment strategies primarily determine productivity. Tall trees with dense wood likely sustain larger leaf area and canopy access, enhancing GPP through light capture and long-lived biomass (Falster & Westoby, 2003; Phillips & Brienen, 2017). The SHAP beeswarm for UNLIM confirms this, showing high height values exerting strong positive effects on predicted GPP, while leaf C:N values cluster near zero, indicating negligible directional influence under unlimited N supply (see Figure 19).

Under the NLIM case, the model's emphasis shows an increase in leaf functional traits, with leaf C:N and SLA increasing in importance (see Figure 17). In the NLIM SHAP plots, leaf C:N exhibits a clear negative relationship, where high (N-limited) values suppress predicted GPP (see Figure 19). This shift reflects the growing importance of foliar nutrient economics under N limitation. When N is scarce, trees with low leaf N (high C:N) face direct biochemical constraints on photosynthesis because N is a key component of Rubisco and chlorophyll. This pattern aligns with experimental and modeling studies, which show that N availability regulates photosynthetic capacity and carbon assimilation efficiency in tropical forests (Domingues et al., 2010; Posada et al., 2012).

At Manaus, large-tree feature importance values for both structural (height, wood density) and foliar traits (SLA, C:N) declined from the decade 1940–1950 to 2004–2014 under both N treatments, indicating that trait–productivity linkages weakened over time (see Figure 18). This pattern aligns with the global meta-analysis by Hu et al. (2025), which confirms that along with low nutrient availability, warming and drought

in forests under elevated CO₂ significantly (increasing environmental stress) decrease biomass productivity in communities dominated by slow-growing species.

This long-term functional weakening is supported by the metabolic shifts demonstrated by Song et al. (2025), who investigated how plants respond when they receive more light, in a manner that mimics changes in the forest canopy, shifting from rapid growth to a more conservative strategy. They found that when plants experience higher light levels, they switch to a resource-conserving strategy (slow growth). This strategy is characterized by building tougher leaves with low SLA (a 24.78% decrease compared to the acquisition strategy) and storing more carbon (C content increased from 49% to 62%). At the same time, they increase the activity of sugar-producing enzymes and boost defense-related enzymes. This "defense-for-growth trade-off" causes nitrogen to move away from growth processes, such as building photosynthetic proteins, and toward producing defensive compounds.

Similarly, Su et al. (2024) add that although traits such as SLA and stomatal conductance are still important in the short term, their influence is limited by environmental constraints on photosynthesis.

Recent modelling work shows that leaf trait plasticity can alter tropical tree growth and competitive outcomes under elevated CO₂, indicating that trees with lower leaf N content grow less under high CO₂, but this negative effect can be mitigated if leaf thickness increases simultaneously (Kovenock et al., 2021). Manaus results suggest that under post-1950 acceleration time CO₂ enrichment, tropical trees may adjust multiple leaf traits in concert, reducing the direct influence of individual traits on GPP.

However, there is still a need to examine these environmental stressors (temperature, light, radiance, and precipitation) in detail to understand the changes in the trade-off mechanisms of plant traits.

4.5 Trait Coordination and Model Representation: SLA-LNC Relationships

The negative relation between LNC and SLA found in both the global TRY dataset and LPJmL-FIT simulations found in this thesis shows a fundamental trade-off along the leaf economics spectrum (Wright et al., 2004). This pattern of negative slope matches with earlier studies confirming that leaves with greater LNC have lower SLA which are optimized for resource conservation (Poorter et al., 2009; Reich et al., 1997).

The LPJmL-FIT simulations yielded substantially steeper slopes at the tropical forest sites, suggesting that the model accentuates the inverse relationship between LNC and SLA more than empirical data from the TRY database (see Figure 21). The LPJmL-FIT model shows a much steeper inverse relationship between LNC and SLA in comparison to the TRY database slope, because its strong competition for light and water rapidly eliminates plants with suboptimal trait combinations. The traits are initially assigned randomly, but the survival depends on how well each combination fits local conditions, thereby pushing tree individuals toward more carbon-efficient strategies. This selection strategy produces a narrower trait range than observed in real ecosystems, where natural variation allows for a broader spectrum of SLA–LNC relationships (Sakschewski et al., 2015). This suggests that modelled trait plasticity may be overly constrained (see relationship equations no. 19, 20, and 21 in the methods section), leading to exaggerated declines in LNC with increasing SLA (see Figures 22, 23). Sometimes absence of local resource and microenvironmental niche diversity in the vegetation models overly constrains the trade-offs leading to narrower gradients (Reich, 2014).

Because the model explicitly links leaf-N content and SLA via the leaf economics spectrum under N limitation, the inverse relationship under dynamic CO₂ is an emergent property of the model rather than a preset slope. This feature enables us to derive leaf-trait distributions and trait–trait slopes directly from the model (rather than calibrating them post hoc), thereby providing a novel capacity to test hypothetical changes in trait-strategy space under global change.

4.6 Interpreting the Beta Factor in the Context of Nitrogen Limitation

The rolling-window approach by S. Wang et al. (2020) estimates β dynamically by regressing GPP against CO₂ across moving temporal windows, thereby capturing short-term variations in sensitivity (see detailed method in section 2.5.2). In this study simulations, this method revealed a pronounced historical decline in β (from ~25% to 13–17% per 100 ppm CO₂)(see Figure 16), consistent with the study of global weakening of CFE from 1982 to 2015 at a rate from 5 to 10 times greater than the terrestrial carbon model (S. Wang et al., 2020).

This conclusion by S. Wang et al. (2020) has generated a substantial debate centered on four key areas: data reliability, methodological flaws, proxy limitations, and model comparison issues. Critics argued the finding was not robust, primarily due to systematic biases in the pre-2000 NIRv data from satellites (Frankenberg et al., 2021). Moreover, the methods to evaluate regression coefficient β failed to robustly separate CO₂ effects from climatic parameters such as vapor pressure deficit and temperature, with DGVM tests showing poor consistency between β and the true CFE (Sang et al., 2021; Z. Zhu et al., 2021).

However, S. Wang et al. (2021) defended their findings, by showing that, even after correcting for biases and using alternative datasets, the global decline in the CFE remained significant. They also argued that model based factorial simulations cannot directly comparable to observational CFE due to land–atmosphere feedbacks, and lack of crucial nutrient limitations, confirming the robustness of the observed decline.

In the second method, the relativized β -factor (β_{in}) method proposed by Walker et al. (2021) and Chen et al. (2022) provides a more aggregated, elasticity-based measure of long-term CO₂ sensitivity. The historical increase in β from this study (0.61 for UNLIM, 0.50 for NLIM) aligns with site-scale observations across 632 sites of eddy covariance network, found by Chen et al. (2022) shows a strong increasing GPP trend of a positive β value of 1.24 globally. While these values of β_{in} , incorporating the combined effects of both CO₂ and climate variability, are quite high, they correspond to several other published indirect apparent GPP proxies (Walker et al., 2021).

The tree growth stimulated by rising CO₂ has continued historically (the gross gain), but the overall carbon sink is declining (the net effect). Tropical inventory data from Amazon and Africa confirm that continuous forest growth has increased over the past three decades, and rising forest carbon density (Hubau et al., 2020). However, the net carbon uptake of intact tropical forests peaked in the 1990s and has since fallen by 31%, with the Amazon sink projected to reach zero by around 2035 (Hubau et al., 2020; Pan et al., 2024).

For the future climate scenarios, especially SSP370 (see Figure 16, Table 3), both approaches from the papers and the results of this thesis show further decline in the CFE. Decreasing future CFE has been observed by some other studies also, which

revealed that rising temperatures and despite a significant increase in Water use efficiency, the trees are not benefiting, which overestimates the fertilization effect (Laffitte et al., 2022; Pan et al., 2024; C. Zhu et al., 2023).

In their brief synthesis report regarding CFE, Lapola et al. (2025) concluded from other studies combining data and models that there is no certainty regarding this effect found on the tropical forests' overall growth and survival. Instead, it can lead to adverse shifts in forest conditions, potentially reducing canopy transpiration and altering the Amazon's hydrological cycle.

Walker et al. (2021) in their review, show that tropical forests have historically expressed a CO₂-fertilization signal in regions such as Amazon ($\beta = 1.2 \pm 0.6$) and tropical Africa ($\beta = 0.69 \pm 0.63$). But they argue the CFE is likely to weaken because the direct physiological response of GPP by C₃ trees (in the tropics) to rising CO₂ is expected to diminish ($\beta_{\text{direct,historical}} = 0.60 \pm 0.3$ to $\beta_{\text{direct,future}} = 0.46 \pm 0.2$), a pattern consistent with the Farquhar photosynthesis model (Farquhar et al., 1980), where CO₂-driven gains in assimilation fall as canopies shift from CO₂-limited to increasingly light-limited conditions. Nutrient constraints are intensifying, and negative temperature-related effects, as well as mortality, are increasing in the Amazon, which would further constrain the future growth. They also acknowledge the fact that the evidence is currently "insufficient to robustly evaluate how enhanced CO₂ affects late-successional and tropical forests", underscoring the high uncertainty in tropical CFE predictions, but concluding that a decline is highly likely.

The discrepancies between the two β formulations are not just numerical but conceptual. The rolling-window β captures instantaneous or short-term sensitivities, influenced by transient physiological responses and climate variability, while the relativized β_{in} integrates cumulative, system-level adjustments over longer timescales, including acclimation and soil feedback.

CFE is real and beneficial, but its long-term future is uncertain, requiring intensive, integrated, and well-designed research efforts to improve predictive understanding. So, in conclusion, under these uncertain future climate scenarios, it becomes important to carefully design methods that best represent the fertilisation effects on the complex tropical forests.

4.7 Nutrient-Carbon Interaction Limits: Implications for Future DGVMs and Tropical Forest Resilience

The thesis findings provide important insights into N dynamics, playing a crucial role in constraining productivity in the tropics. However, the current version of the LPJmL-FIT model also has limitations.

Firstly, in the tropical rainforests, P is the most common nutrient limitation in vast lowland tropical forests due to the extreme weathering of ancient soils, which binds and depletes P stores (Giller, 2020; Vitousek, 1984). This P scarcity constrains tree growth and ecosystem processes, a finding confirmed by fertilization experiments in the Amazon (Cunha et al., 2022). However, many forest biomes like Cerrado exhibit co-limitation by N and P, with P availability often modulating the entire N cycle (Vallicrosa et al., 2023).

A study by Fleischer et al. (2019), using 14 terrestrial ecosystem models that simulate the planned Free-Air CO₂ Enrichment (AmazonFACE) experiment, demonstrated that including P feedback in terrestrial ecosystem models reduces the projected CO₂-driven biomass gain by approximately 50% compared to only C-N models. Furthermore, Dantas de Paula et al. (2025) using the CNP version of the LPJ-GUESS model found that P limitation, especially in tropical regions, is projected to increase globally (while N limitation decreases), suggesting that the CO₂ fertilization effect will be limited by P availability. Therefore, to provide robust and realistic projections of tropical forest resilience and capacity as a carbon sink under future climate scenarios, the future development of LPJmL-FIT should prioritize the comprehensive integration of the P cycle and its cascading effects on N cycling and trait-based plant adaptations.

Secondly, the unique contribution of the LPJmL-FIT model to projecting tropical forest resilience lies in establishing tree individuals with a continuous range of empirically constrained traits, allowing community structure to emerge as a property determined by environmental and direct competitive filtering (Sakschewski et al., 2015). However, the model still struggles with somewhat strict or strong competitive filtering based on rigorous, implemented trade-offs, which could be improved for future model development.

Including P limitations along with N in the LPJmL-FIT model will vary results, especially for tropical regions. It would be too complex to predict or guess at this stage how the model would behave, as it would require multiple tests and experiments with the model. However, models like CLM-CNP showing significantly reduced NPP bias in Amazon sites (from 15% to 7%) and correctly capturing the spatial trend of productivity being limited by P availability can give us a closer look at possible outcomes of models (Yang et al., 2014). Furthermore, the LPJ-GUESS-NTD model confirmed that emergent trait gradients and realistic NPP levels in tropical mountains rely entirely on nutrient activation, demonstrating that the removal of P acquisition mechanisms, such as mycorrhiza-mediated uptake, reduced NPP by 61-72% (Dantas de Paula et al., 2021). The ORCHIDEE-CN-P model also confirmed that CNP models are essential for more realistic predictions of future land carbon uptake, suggesting that P's importance will increase as CO₂ concentration rises (Goll et al., 2017).

Thirdly, to improve high computational demands, parameter uncertainty, and limited realism of DGVMs, machine learning and model–data integration techniques are essential (Bagnara et al., 2019). By coupling DGVMs with a statistical framework, neural networks, and Bayesian models, researchers can emulate complex biogeochemical processes with up to 95% faster computation (Natel et al., 2025; Fer et al., 2018). These approaches using satellite and flux data can capture key environmental controls, such as soil moisture and temperature, on phenology and carbon turnover (Forkel et al., 2014; Forkel et al., 2019).

Fourthly, to quantify the CFE more accurately in DGVMs, there is a need to expand eddy covariance observations in tropical regions (Chen et al., 2022). Based on 138 elevated CO₂ experiments, the empirically derived CFE rate (25 ± 4 PgC/100 ppm⁻¹) is substantially lower than DGVM estimates (Terrer et al., 2019). Large-scale field FACE experiments can offer vital empirical data on ecosystem responses to elevated CO₂, nutrient dynamics, helping refine and calibrate DGVM representations of carbon dynamics, and validating key outcomes with real-world datasets (Norby et al., 2016; Terrer et al., 2019).

5. Conclusion

This thesis examined the effects of nitrogen limitations on productivity and flexible plant traits in the tropical biomes of Brazil using the LPJmL-FIT model.

When addressing the first research question, how the N limitation in the LPJmL-FIT model simulations influences the CO₂ fertilization effect and regulates vegetation productivity dynamics under climate change in tropical forests, this thesis found that N limitation consistently reduces GPP, and VegC acts as a dampener on the CFE. The historical 10% reduction in GPP increased to around 12 % under future climate-change scenarios and confirmed the concept of Progressive Nitrogen Limitation, particularly in the Amazon and Cerrado regions. The beta factor analysis and review of existing studies explore how the CFE weakens over time, particularly under high-emission scenarios. These findings align with empirical and modeling evidence suggesting that omitting N limitations leads to overestimation of the vegetation's capacity to absorb carbon.

The second question examined how relationships between plant functional traits reflect adjustments under elevated CO₂ and N limitation. The random forest model revealed that the traits predicting productivity shift under nitrogen stress as under UNLIM case, GPP was predicted mostly by structural traits (height, wood density), while under N-limitation, the emphasis moved to foliar functional traits like leaf C:N and SLA, showing that nutrient-use efficiency becomes the main physiological constraint.

Furthermore, the third question explored how N availability and tree traits influence ecosystem functioning at the tree level, and what model predictions indicate about forest adaptation and ecosystem responses to future climate change. At the tree level, N availability governs photosynthetic capacity, carbon assimilation, and tissue development, directly impacting growth rates and competitive dynamics. The model results indicate that the N limitation drove compositional shifts favoring lower-biomass, nutrient-efficient C4 grasses over high-biomass evergreen trees indicating adaptation at the cost of overall carbon storage, while the critical importance of BNF in alleviating N stress was highlighted; however, future projections show a strong decline in the CFE, suggesting intensifying combined nutrient and water shortages will make Brazilian ecosystems more vulnerable to future climate change.

Finally, to improve model realism, future model development should include processes that are equally important in tropical biomes, such as i) including the essential integration of the P cycle to avoid overestimating future carbon stocks in the tropics, ii) refinement of the trait trade-off equations to allow for a broader, more realistic spectrum of functional strategies, and iii) the incorporation of machine learning techniques to manage computational demands, and data-integration from field experiments reduce uncertainties of model parameters, especially trait-related parameters.

Exploring regional differences or enabling the crop and managed land modules in LPJmL-FIT would allow the model to be forced with socio-economic land-use scenarios. Upgrading the model studies to realistic land-use scenarios would better capture how nitrogen inputs and losses vary across agricultural and managed lands from fertilizer and biological fixation to harvest, erosion, and leaching. This would improve estimates of how nitrogen limits CO₂ fertilization and provide a more complete picture of carbon-nitrogen fluxes across Brazil.

Nutrient limitations play a crucial role in determining the capacity of tropical forests to sequester carbon, especially under climate change scenarios. This study, which explicitly includes nitrogen dynamics as a proxy for nutrient limitation in tropical forests of Brazil, highlights that nitrogen limitations reduce productivity (by 10%-19%) across all climate change scenarios and, consequently, dampen the CFE. Under nitrogen stress, forests adjust their plant functional traits and strategies, leading to potential shifts in vegetation composition across Amazon, Cerrado, Caatinga, and other Brazilian biomes. Uncertain future climate change scenarios (mainly intense droughts, high temperatures) and rapid land-use pattern changes (which would affect nutrient availability in soil) in Brazil make the biomes there more vulnerable. In this context, DGVMs like LPJmL-FIT, with their flexible plant trait mechanisms, along with nitrogen limitations, play a vital role in projecting the carbon absorption dynamics of tropical forests. Further enhancements to the model could inform policymakers and the scientific community in developing the best mechanisms for sustainable forest management.

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis is my own work and that, to the best of my knowledge, it contains no material previously published or substantially overlapping with material submitted for the award of any other degree at any institution, except where due acknowledgment is made in the text. According to the TUM guidelines on the use of AI tools, I utilized large language model (ChatGPT, version 5.1) and Grammarly solely for paraphrasing, linguistic, and grammatical improvements. No content, ideas, or literature were generated by these tools.

Berlin, 01.12.2025

Place, Date

Sangita Chouhan

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Supplementary Figures

Figure 24: Absolute VegC values in Pg C yr^{-1} simulated by LPJmL-FIT under limited nitrogen (NLIM) (black solid line) and unlimited nitrogen (UNLIM) (blue solid line) conditions in Brazil. In both factorial experiments, the trend (black dashed line for NLIM and blue dashed line for UNLIM) is statistically significant ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$). The statistics for increasing trends using Sen's slope is shown in the figures for Historical (upper panel), SSP126 (middle panel), and SSP370 (lower panel).

Brazil Biome GPP Trends - Historical

Wet biomes (UNLIM): tau=0.73, Sen=0.016
 Wet biomes (NLIM): tau=0.83, Sen=0.014
 Dry biomes (UNLIM): tau=0.66, Sen=-0.009
 Dry biomes (NLIM): tau=0.74, Sen=0.008

Brazil Biome GPP Trends - SSP126

Wet biomes (UNLIM): tau=0.17, Sen=0.005
 Wet biomes (NLIM): tau=0.43, Sen=0.009
 Dry biomes (UNLIM): tau=0.13, Sen=0.002
 Dry biomes (NLIM): tau=0.25, Sen=0.004

Brazil Biome GPP Trends - SSP370

Wet biomes (UNLIM): tau=0.84, Sen=0.059
 Wet biomes (NLIM): tau=0.85, Sen=0.045
 Dry biomes (UNLIM): tau=0.74, Sen=0.033
 Dry biomes (NLIM): tau=0.76, Sen=0.025

Biome Type ■ Dry biomes_NLIM ■ Dry biomes_UNLIM ■ Wet biomes_NLIM ■ Wet biomes_UNLIM

Figure 25: Absolute GPP values by the LPJmL-FIT model in PgC/yr for the Wet biomes (Amazon + Mata Atlantica) (NLIM=black solid line, UNLIM=blue solid line) and Dry biomes (Cerrado+Caatinga+Patanaal+Pampa) (NLIM=orange solid line, UNLIM=green solid line) for 3 scenarios: Historical (upper panel), SSP126 (middle panel), and SSP370 (lower panel). Here, it's clearly seen that wet biomes contribute more to annual productivity in Brazil. Also the Sen's slope for UNLIM cases are higher than NLIM cases, as shown by dashed lines. The statistics for the trends is mentioned in the figure.

Figure 26: FPC plots of tropical evergreen broad-leaved trees for NLIM and UNLIM cases for a) Historical (first row), averaged over 1985 to 2014, b) SSP126 (second row), averaged over 2015 to 2100, c) SSP370 (third row), averaged over 2015 to 2100. The 1st column figure represents the UNLIM case, the 2nd column maps represent the NLIM case, and the 3rd column map shows the difference between the NLIM and UNLIM for all in all three rows. FPC is a dimensionless fractional cover (0–1). The orange-to-red scale indicates high foliage cover of tropical evergreen broad-leaved trees, while white and yellow indicate low coverage. In the difference maps (3rd column), blue indicates high coverage for the UNLIM case, whereas red and orange indicate that NLIM has higher coverage.

Figure 27: FPC plots of Temperate needleleaved evergreen for NLIM and UNLIM cases for a) Historical (first row), averaged over 1985 to 2014, b) SSP126 (second row), averaged over 2015 to 2100, c) SSP370 (third row), averaged over 2015 to 2100. The 1st column figure represents the UNLIM case, the 2nd column maps represent the NLIM case, and the 3rd column map shows the difference between the NLIM and UNLIM for all in all three rows. FPC is a dimensionless fractional cover (0–1). The orange-to-red scale indicates high foliage cover of tropical evergreen broad-leaved trees, while white and yellow indicate low coverage. In the difference maps (3rd column), blue indicates high coverage for the UNLIM case, whereas red and orange indicate that NLIM has higher coverage.

Figure 28: FPC plots of C4 grass for NLIM and UNLIM cases for a) Historical (first row), averaged over 1985 to 2014, b) SSP126 (second row), averaged over 2015 to 2100, c) SSP370 (third row), averaged over 2015 to 2100. The 1st column figure represents the UNLIM case, the 2nd column maps represent the NLIM case, and the 3rd column map shows the difference between the NLIM and UNLIM for all in all three rows. FPC is a dimensionless fractional cover (0–1). The orange-to-red scale indicates high foliage cover of tropical evergreen broad-leaved trees, while white and yellow indicate low coverage. In the difference maps (3rd column), blue indicates high coverage for the UNLIM case, whereas red and orange indicate that NLIM has higher coverage.

Figure 29: Temporal heat density plots of log(SLA) in mm²/mg and log(LNC) in g/m² for UNLIM and NLIM cases for Santarém for the historical period (1850 to 2014). The color intensity (Count) denotes the frequency/density of observations for a given trait value in a given year, with yellow indicating the highest frequency. The overlaid solid black line traces the mean trait value over time.

Figure 30: Temporal heat density plots of $\log(\text{SLA})$ in mm^2/mg and $\log(\text{LNC})$ in g/m^2 for UNLIM and NLIM cases for Manaus for the historical period (1850 to 2014). The color intensity (Count) denotes the frequency/density of observations for a given trait value in a given year, with yellow indicating the highest frequency. The overlaid solid black line traces the mean trait value over time.

Figure 31: Annual Mean Precipitation (mm/day) in Manaus and Santarém (1850–2014). Manaus consistently receives higher annual mean precipitation than Santarém, though both locations exhibit high inter-annual variability.

Figure 32: Annual Mean Temperature (°C) in Manaus and Santarém (1850–2014). Both sites show a clear long-term warming trend, particularly since the mid-20th century. Manaus consistently records a higher annual mean temperature (approximately 1.5°C to 2°C warmer) than Santarém across the entire observational period.

Supplementary Tables

Table 5: Global sum time average table, for historical years (1985-2014), where cell-time values of each variable are weighted by reference area, summed, and then averaged over time. LPJLFUN= UNLIM case results; LPJFIL= NLIM case results; diff2base: Difference (NLIM-UNLIM); diff_%=Difference percentage

variable	unit	baseline: LPJLFUN	under_test: LPJFIL	diff2base: LPJFIL	diff_%: LPJFIL
veg	[GtC]	47.33	44.08	-3.248	-6.862
fpc\$natural stand fraction	[1e6 ha]	351	351	0	0
fpc\$temperate needleleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	49.3	60.18	10.88	22.06
fpc\$temperate broadleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	10	8.6	-1.4	-14
fpc\$tropical broadleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	185.9	176.2	-9.682	-5.209
fpc\$tropical c4 grass	[1e6 ha]	16.74	21.79	5.055	30.2
fpc\$temperate broadleaved summergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	4.312	2.051	-2.261	-52.44
fpc\$boreal needleleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
fpc\$boreal broadleaved summergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
fpc\$boreal needleleaved summergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
fpc\$temperate c3 grass	[1e6 ha]	0.8298	0.5969	-0.233	-28.07
fpc\$polar c3 grass	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
npp	[GtC yr-1]	3.1	2.735	-0.3658	-11.8
gpp	[GtC yr-1]	7.517	6.74	-0.7764	-10.33
transp	[km3 yr-1]	2577	2177	-399.8	-15.51

Table 6: Global sum time average table, for SSP126 years (2015-2100), where cell-time values of each variable are weighted by reference area, summed, and then averaged over time. LPJLFUN= UNLIM case results; LPJFIL= NLIM case results; diff2base: Difference (NLIM-UNLIM); diff_%=Difference percentage

variable	unit	baseline: LPJLFUN	under_test: LPJFIL	diff2base: LPJLFIL	diff_%: LPJLFIL
vegC	[GtC]	60.36	50.62	-9.736	-16.13
fpc\$natural stand fraction	[1e6 ha]	351	351	0	0
fpc\$temperate needleleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	52.67	66.98	14.31	27.16
fpc\$temperate broadleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	10.91	10.23	-0.6744	-6.182
fpc\$tropical broadleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	193.7	171.3	-22.4	-11.56
fpc\$tropical c4 grass	[1e6 ha]	12.93	18.66	5.729	44.3
fpc\$temperate broadleaved summergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	4.34	2.286	-2.055	-47.34
fpc\$boreal needleleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
fpc\$boreal broadleaved summergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
fpc\$boreal needleleaved summergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
fpc\$temperate c3 grass	[1e6 ha]	0.777	0.5552	-0.2218	-28.55
fpc\$polar c3 grass	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
npp	[GtC yr-1]	3.443	3.022	-0.4206	-12.22
gpp	[GtC yr-1]	8.392	7.519	-0.8722	-10.39
transp	[km3 yr-1]	2651	2267	-384.1	-14.49

Table 7: Global sum time average table, for SSP370 years (2015-2100), where cell-time values of each variable are weighted by reference area, summed, and then averaged over time. LPJLFUN= UNLIM case results; LPJFIL= NLIM case results; diff2base: Difference (NLIM-UNLIM); diff_%=Difference percentage

variable	unit	baseline: LPJLFUN	under_test: LPJFIL	diff2base: LPJFIL	diff_%: LPJFIL
veg	[GtC]	67.59	54.68	-12.91	-19.1
fpc\$natural stand fraction	[1e6 ha]	351	351	0	0
fpc\$temperate needleleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	55.3	70.13	14.83	26.82
fpc\$temperate broadleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	11.07	10.91	-0.1572	-1.42
fpc\$tropical broadleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	200.9	174.3	-26.64	-13.26
fpc\$tropical c4 grass	[1e6 ha]	11.72	17.07	5.345	45.61
fpc\$temperate broadleaved summergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	4.642	2.477	-2.165	-46.65
fpc\$boreal needleleaved evergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
fpc\$boreal broadleaved summergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
fpc\$boreal needleleaved summergreen tree	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
fpc\$temperate c3 grass	[1e6 ha]	0.5533	0.4462	-0.1072	-19.37
fpc\$polar c3 grass	[1e6 ha]	0	0	0	NaN
npp	[GtC yr-1]	3.803	3.264	-0.539	-14.17
gpp	[GtC yr-1]	9.314	8.143	-1.171	-12.57
transp	[km3 yr-1]	2660	2236	-424.2	-15.94